

D1.3

Analysis of synergies and trade-offs

CIRCE

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ABBREVIATIONS

D1.3: Analysis of synergies and trade-offs, 28/04/2023

CBE	Circular bioeconomy
EU	European Union
LCA	Life cycle analysis
PE	Polyethylene
PP	Polypropylene
PLA	Polylactic acid
PHA	Polyhydroxyalkanoates
PET	Polyethylene terephthalate
PEF	Polyethylene furanoate
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals

Executive Summary

This deliverable has been prepared under Task 1.4 “Analysis of synergies and trade-offs” in the Work package WP1 – “Review and analysis of schemes and labels” of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project. In the context of WP1, the objective of Task 1.4 is to deliver a qualitative analysis identifying the trade-offs and synergies of selected biobased value chains within sustainability dimensions, which include economic, social, and environmental aspects.

In this work, a range of sustainability targets from the seventeen sustainable development goals (SDGs) defined by the United Nations that are most relevant for industrial biobased products were selected and categorized into four main areas, namely: Environmental, Circularity, Social and Economic. A total of 85 SDG targets were selected linking to the sustainability principles and criteria collated for industrial biobased systems (as part of D1.2). In this project, six major sectors are considered (chemicals, construction, plastics, textiles, woodworking, and pulp & paper) as defined in D1.1. Three to five value chains were selected per sector to perform the analysis of synergies and trade-offs (a total of 25). These value chains serve as examples as representations of the sectors for their evaluation and are not linked with the selection of the most representative biobased chains in the project which is carried out within Task 2.1 following the analytic hierarchy process. The selection of the representative value chains was based on various aspects such as: existence of sustainability certification schemes, production size in Europe, economic importance in Europe, and potential to replace fossil-based products (either providing a drop-in solution by replacing the feedstock, or via novel dedicated pathways from biomass with no petrochemical equivalent). Besides the traditional ones (e.g., cotton for textiles), emerging biobased value chains concerning novel technologies (e.g., fibres from recycled textiles and microfibrillated cellulosic materials) were taken into consideration. From the 85 matching SDG targets, 43 were found applicable to the representative biobased value chains of each sector.

Each value chain was evaluated qualitatively with respect to each SDG target to identify either positive (+) or negative (-) correlation which refers to synergies or trade-offs. For some, neither a synergy nor trade-off was seen, which was marked as (+/-). The SDG targets that were not applicable to a certain value chain were marked as (na). These evaluations were made based on information and official data publicly available online, such as EU technical reports, the PRODCOM database, academic literature, published life cycle analyses (LCAs) of value chains considered, news articles, and experts' opinions. A final score was obtained per value chain based on the qualitative assessment, and concluding remarks are presented based on results per sector and per value chain within each sector. The results show that high synergies are seen for the SDG targets with the assessed biobased value chains, particularly the ones using waste as feedstock (instead of primary resources such as starch crops, sugar crops, and virgin wood). Technological advances and a more holistic view are enabling the replacement of resource-intensive materials and chemicals, traditionally derived from petroleum, by solutions obtained from biological resources that might have other positive properties such as recyclability, biodegradability, and non-toxicity.

1. Introduction

Transitioning from a fossil-based economy to a biobased economy involves replacing conventional fossil-based products with their biobased alternatives. There is an ever-increasing push from society and governmental actors to promote such a shift, as novel technologies and circular biobased value chains can potentially decarbonize industrial sectors heavily dependent on petroleum, as well as provide additional environmental benefits by lowering greenhouse gas emissions and creating positive socio-technical transformations in the society, such as rural development and technology transfer to underdeveloped regions and communities. As highlighted by the European Commission “European Bioeconomy needs to have sustainability and circularity at its heart”. Accordingly, the term circular bioeconomy (CBE) has been recently introduced to intertwine the bioeconomy and circular economy concepts.¹

While the overall benefits of biobased economy and promising case studies of biobased value chains have been extensively reported, their potential trade-offs and negative impacts must also be investigated. It is not correct to assume that the biobased economy is inherently sustainable without an in-depth analysis of the impacts of each value chain, from an environmental, economic, and social perspectives. For instance, the main points of attention of biobased value chains are related to increased pressure on water bodies and natural ecosystems, deforestation, competition for land (and with food production), eutrophication, acidification and high energy use.² Furthermore, there is an ongoing discussion on how following a “linear, business-as-usual” approach, i.e., not considering circularity principles and the limited natural resources available on Earth, can lead to unsustainable value chains regardless of their biobased character. As elegantly defined by Tan, et al.³, “A sustainable bioeconomy goes beyond simply switching fossil resources with renewable, biological resources. It requires low-carbon energy inputs, sustainable supply chains, and promising disruptive conversion technologies for the sustainable transformation of renewable bioresources to high-value bio-based products, materials, and fuels.” Other important aspects of the transition to the bioeconomy involve defining a set of consistent, standardized metrics for various products and industries (e.g., certification labels and schemes) and applying a multidisciplinary approach on the design and implementation of novel value chains. Such need for standardization goes as far as for the definition of concepts that are often used interchangeably, such as “circular bioeconomy”, “circular economy”, “bioeconomy”, and “sustainability”.

A recent review on the EU bioeconomy clusters¹ highlights important advances on the development of integrated biorefineries using residues as a resource, as well as on material and high-value applications for its products. Nonetheless, little focus is still given to the end-of-life aspects of the biobased products. While some key challenges for implementing circular strategies are technical (e.g., some biobased materials such as thermosets are challenging to recycle and repurpose), policies and regulations play a crucial role on incentivizing secondary markets and circularity. Overall, social aspects, circular product design, and definition of final use for biobased product streams seem to be underrepresented in the bioeconomy literature. Furthermore, the information is often fragmented and focused either in a purely technical/economic/social/circular aspect of the value chain, rendering the analysis incomplete from a sustainability perspective, which encompasses all said aspects.

In this context, this deliverable aims at assessing selected representative biobased value chains using a more multidisciplinary approach, by considering SDG targets within four main sustainability dimensions (environmental, circularity, social and economic). While being a qualitative assessment based in often general and fragmented information available per sector and/or value chain, the results here discussed highlight the main bottlenecks and benefits identified in the sustainability space for said value chains, serving as base for further analyses and developments within the

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project and beyond. This deliverable follows D1.1 that presented a classification of biological resources and biobased products related to the targeted industrial sectors, and D1.2 where a methodology for reviewing schemes and labels were set and used in reviewing the selected existing sustainability schemes and labels relevant to biobased value chains.

To guide the reader throughout this document, the sections of this report are:

- **Chapter 2** describes the methodologies followed to i) link the sustainability dimensions with SDG targets; ii) select representative biobased value chains per sector; and iii) correlate each value chain with the selected SDG targets.
 - **Chapter 3** discusses the results of i) linking the sustainability dimensions with the SDG targets, which led to a selection of targets for the qualitative assessment; and ii) the qualitative assessment itself, which identified synergies and trade-offs between the selected SDG targets and biobased value chains.
 - **Chapter 4** brings the conclusions of this work, and linkage with the subsequent tasks planned for the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project.
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2. Methodology

This section introduces the overall methodology followed and the different steps involved in *i)* linking the sustainability dimensions collected and described in D1.2 to the sustainable development goals (SDGs) and relevant targets within each SDG; *ii)* identifying relevant biobased value chains in each of the six prominent sectors, in alignment with the outputs of T1.1. classification of biological resources and biobased products; and *iii)* analysing synergies and trade-offs of the value chains within the selected SDG targets.

2.1 Methodology followed to link the sustainability dimensions with SDG targets

The dimensions of sustainability have been the subject of study since the concept of sustainable development became popular. The concept of sustainable development is not static. It has evolved in parallel with scientific, technological, and human development, admitting multiple interpretations, progressively remaining as a framework of intentions. Since its origins this concept has been mainly focused on the environmental and economic dimensions and less on the social dimension. Nevertheless, the interaction between the different dimensions and the importance of each of them is now recognized.⁴ Then, the backbone of the concept of sustainable development is based on the three pillars: economics, social and environmental (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Diagram of the pillars of sustainability.

However, in addition to these three sustainability dimensions established, this project has considered an extra pillar within sustainability: circularity (Figure 2).

Circularity is not distinctly considered as a separate dimension or pillar established within sustainability. This is because the principles related to the circular economy, waste management and the use of alternative raw materials, are usually included in the environmental dimension. In this project, circularity was considered as an additional dimension with its own set of principles and criteria. Within the pillar of circularity, the scope has been expanded to include the use of renewable

resources, recyclability, and the use of recycled materials, which have not been specifically or explicitly addressed in the other dimensions so far.

Figure 2. Diagram of the pillars of sustainability considered in this project.

In the deliverable D1.2 “Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels”, sustainability requirements applicable to biological resources and to biobased materials and products, a collation of principles and criteria were made reviewing relevant legislation, standards, certification schemes and studies in the field of sustainable bioeconomy. These criteria and principles have been classified into these four pillars: environmental, circularity, social and economic (Table 1).

Table 1. Sustainability principles and criteria from D1.2 “Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels”.

Dimension	Principles	Criteria
Environmental	Reduce GHG emissions	Lifecycle GHG emissions
	Conserve land with high carbon stock and peatland	Protection of land with high carbon stock
		Protection of peatland
	Promote sustainable forest management	Maintaining forest productivity
	Promote the positive and reduce the negative impacts on ecosystems and biodiversity	Protection of land with a high biodiversity value
		Restoration, preservation and strengthening of biodiversity
	Conserve and protect water resources	Sustainable use of water
		Maintaining and enhancing water quality
	Protect soil quality and productivity	Maintaining and enhancing soil quality
		Use of residual flows
	Implement best practices for the use of (agro)chemicals	Prohibition on the use of hazardous/toxic chemicals
Use, storage, handling and disposal of (agro)chemicals		
Restrict air pollution, promote good air quality	Air quality	
	Restriction on open-air burning	
Limit the risk of Indirect Land Use Change	ILUC Low Risk	
Circularity	Promote responsible waste management	Waste management
		Valorisation of residual flows
	Promote efficient use of energy and material resources	Raw material efficiency
Efficient use of energy		

		Use of renewable and non-renewable sources
	Promote material circularity	Material circularity
Social principle	Labour rights	Child labour
		Forced and compulsory labour
		Fair salary, Remuneration
		Association and collective bargaining rights
		Equal opportunities/discrimination
		Grievance mechanism
	Working conditions	Contract
		Training
		Occupational health and safety
		Harassment, violence
Property and usage rights	Hours of work and overtime	
	Land use rights (including land tenure)	
Wellbeing of the local population	Water use rights	
	Health and safety of local community	
	Local services (health, education, infrastructure, ...) / Prosperity	
	Local values	
Food security	Community involvement	
Economic principle	Financial and economic viability (Economic sustainability, continual improvement)	Financial and economic viability
	Fair business practices, Integrity (fraudulent, deceptive, or dishonest)	Fair business practices, Integrity
	Inclusive economic growth	Local employment and procurement
		Community investment
	Use of knowledge and technology	Compensate indigenous knowledge
		Use of technology
Fair trade and market practices	Fair trade and market practices	
Risk assessment and management	Risk assessment and management	

In this task 1.4, these criteria and principles are used to select the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) targets most relevant for industrial biobased systems.

The SDGs provide a set of global priorities and aspirations for sustainable development in 2030, aiming to unite efforts among governments, businesses, and civil society to eliminate poverty and promote a life of dignity and equal opportunity for all, while respecting the planet's limits. SDGs refer to the three dimensions of sustainable development (economic, social, and environmental) and emphasize the importance of good governance as well as peace and security, which are sometimes referred to as a foundation of sustainable development.⁵ The SDGs are a set of seventeen global goals adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in 2015, as part of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. The goals cover a range of areas including ending poverty and hunger, promoting good health and well-being, achieving gender equality, providing quality education, ensuring access to clean water and sanitation, promoting sustainable economic growth, reducing inequalities, protecting ecosystems and biodiversity, and promoting peaceful and inclusive societies.

Each SDG has a varying number of targets ranging from 6 to 17. In total, there are 169 targets spread across the 17 SDGs (Table 2).

Table 2. Targets of each SDGs.

<p>10. REDUCED INEQUALITIES</p> <p>Reduce inequality within and among countries.</p>	<p>10.1 Reduce income inequalities</p> <p>10.2 Promote universal social, economic and political inclusion.</p> <p>10.3 Ensure equal opportunities and end discrimination.</p> <p>10.4 Adopt fiscal and social policies that promote equality.</p> <p>10.5 Improved regulation of global financial markets and institutions.</p> <p>10.6 Enhanced representation for developing countries in financial institutions.</p> <p>10.7 Responsible and well-managed migration policies.</p> <p>10.8 Special and differential treatment for developing countries.</p> <p>10.9 Encourage development assistance and investment in least developed countries.</p> <p>10.A Reduce transaction costs for migrant remittances.</p>		
<p>11. SUSTAINABLE CITIES AND COMMUNITIES</p> <p>Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable.</p>	<p>11.1 Safe and affordable housing.</p> <p>11.2 Affordable and sustainable transport systems.</p> <p>11.3 Inclusive and sustainable urbanization.</p> <p>11.4 Protect the world's cultural and natural heritage.</p> <p>11.5 Reduce the adverse effects of natural disasters.</p> <p>11.6 Reduce the environmental impact of cities.</p> <p>11.7 Provide Access to safe and inclusive green and public spaces.</p> <p>11.A Strong national and regional development planning.</p> <p>11.B Implement policies for inclusion resource efficiency and disaster risk reduction.</p> <p>11.C Support least developed countries in sustainable and resilient building.</p>		
<p>3. GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING</p> <p>Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages.</p>	<p>3.1 Reduce maternal mortality.</p> <p>3.2 End all preventable deaths under 5 years of age.</p> <p>3.3 Fight communicable diseases.</p> <p>3.4 Reduce mortality from non-communicable diseases and promote mental health.</p> <p>3.5 Prevent and treat substance abuse.</p> <p>3.6 Reduce road injuries and deaths.</p> <p>3.7 Universal access to sexual and reproductive care, family planning and education.</p> <p>3.8 Achieve universal health coverage.</p>		<p>12.1 Implement the 10-year sustainable consumption and production framework.</p> <p>12.2 Sustainable management and use of natural resources.</p> <p>12.3 Halve global per capita food waste.</p> <p>12.4 Responsible management of chemicals and waste.</p>

	<p>3.9 Reduce illnesses and death from hazardous chemicals and pollution.</p> <p>3.A Implement the who framework convention in tobacco control.</p> <p>3.B Support research, development and universal access to affordable vaccines and medicines.</p> <p>3.C Increase health financing and support health workforce in developing countries.</p>	<p>12. RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION</p> <p>Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns.</p>	<p>12.5 Substantially reduce waste generation</p> <p>12.6 Encourage companies to adopt sustainable practices and sustainability reporting.</p> <p>12.7 Promote sustainable public procurement practices.</p> <p>12.8 Promote universal understanding of sustainable lifestyles</p> <p>12.A Support developing countries' scientific and technological capacity for sustainable consumption and production</p> <p>12.B Develop and implement tools to monitor sustainable tourism</p> <p>12.C Remove market distortion that encourage wasteful consumption.</p>
<p>13. CLIMATE ACTION</p> <p>Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts.</p>	<p>13.1 Strengthen resilience and adaptative capacity to climate related disasters.</p> <p>13.2 Integrate climate change measures into policies and planning</p> <p>13.3 Build knowledge and capacity to climate change</p> <p>13.A Implement the UN Framework connection on climate change</p> <p>13.B Promote mechanisms to raise capacity for planning and management.</p>		
<p>14. LIFE BELOW WATER</p> <p>Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development.</p>	<p>14.1 Reduce marine pollution</p> <p>14.2 Protect and restore ecosystems</p> <p>14.3 Reduce Ocean acidification</p> <p>14.4 Sustainable fishing</p> <p>14.5 Conserve coastal and marine areas</p> <p>14.6 End subsidies contributing to overfishing</p> <p>14.7 Increase the economic benefits from sustainable use of marine resources.</p> <p>14.A Increase scientific knowledge, research and technology for ocean health</p> <p>14.B Support small scale fishers</p>		

	5.9 Adopt and strengthen policies and enforceable legislation for gender equality		14.C Implement and enforce international sea law
<p>15. LIFE OF LAND</p> <p>Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and biodiversity loss.</p>	<p>14.C Implement and enforce international sea law</p> <p>15.1 Conserve and restore terrestrial and freshwater ecosystem</p> <p>15.2 End deforestation and restore degraded forests.</p> <p>15.3 End desertification and restore degraded land</p> <p>15.4 Ensure conservation of mountain ecosystem</p> <p>15.5 Protect biodiversity and natural habitats.</p> <p>15.6 Promote Access to genetic resources and fair sharing of the benefits.</p> <p>15.7 Eliminate poaching and trafficking of protected species.</p> <p>15.8 Prevent invasive alien species on land</p> <p>15.9 Integrate ecosystems in government planning.</p> <p>15.A Increase financial resources to conserve and sustainably use ecosystem and biodiversity</p> <p>15.B Finance and incentivize forest management</p> <p>15.C Combat global poaching and trafficking</p>		
<p>16. PACE, JUSTICE, AND INSTITUTIONS</p> <p>Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, provide access to justice for all and build effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels.</p>	<p>16.1 Reduce violence everywhere</p> <p>16.2 Protect children from abuse, exploitation, trafficking and violence</p> <p>16.3 Promote the rule of law and ensure equal access to justice</p> <p>16.4 Combat organized crime and illicit financial and arms flows</p> <p>16.5 Substantially reduce corruption and bribery</p> <p>16.6 Develop effective, accountable, and transparent institutions</p> <p>16.7 Ensure responsive, inclusive, and representative decision-making</p> <p>16.8 Strengthen the participation in global governance</p> <p>16.9 Provide universal legal identity</p> <p>16.A Ensure public access to information and protect fundamental freedoms</p> <p>16.B Strengthen national institutions to prevent violence and combat terrorism and crime</p> <p>16.C Promote and enforce non-discriminatory laws and policies</p>		
<p>8. DECENT WORK AND ECONOMIC GROWTH</p>	<p>8.1 Sustainable economic growth.</p> <p>8.2 Diversify, innovate and upgrade for economic productivity.</p> <p>8.3 Promote policies to support job creation and growing enterprises.</p> <p>8.4 Improve resource efficiency in consumption and production.</p> <p>8.5 Full employment and decent work with equal pay.</p>		

<p>8. DECENT WORK AND ECONOMIC GROWTH</p> <p>Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all.</p>	8.6 Promote youth employment, education and training.	<p>17. PARTNERSHIP FOR THE GOALS</p> <p>Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development.</p>	17.1 Mobilize resources to improve domestic revenue collection
	8.7 End modern slavery, trafficking and child labour.		17.2 Implement all development assistance commitments
	8.8 Protect labour rights and promote safe working environments.		17.3 Mobilize financial resources for developing countries
	8.9 Promote beneficial and sustainable tourism.		17.4 Assist developing countries in attaining debt sustainability
	8.A Universal access to banking, insurance and financial services.		17.5 Invest in least developed countries
	8.B Increase aid for trade support.		17.6 Knowledge sharing and cooperation for access to science, technology and innovation.
	8.C Develop a global youth employment strategy.		17.7 Promote sustainable technologies to developing countries
<p>9. INDUSTRY AND INFRASTRUCTURE</p> <p>Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation.</p>	9.1 Develop sustainable, resilient, and inclusive infrastructures.		17.8 Strengthen the science, technology and innovation capacity for least developed countries
	9.2 Promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization.		17.9 Enhance SDG capacity in developing countries
	9.3 Increase Access to financial services and markets.		17.A Promote a universal trading system under the WTO
	9.4 Upgrade all industries and infrastructures for sustainability.		17.B Increase the exports of developing countries
	9.5 Enhance research and upgrade industrial technologies.		17.C Remove trade barriers for least developed countries
	9.6 Facilitate sustainable infrastructure development for developing countries		17.D Enhance global macroeconomic stability
	9.7 Support domestic technology development and industrial diversification		17.E Enhance policy coherence for sustainable development
	9.8 Universal Access to information and communications technology.	17.F Respect national leadership to implement policies for the sustainable development goals	
		17.G Enhance the global partnership for sustainable development	
		17.H Encourage effective partnerships	
		17.I Enhance availability of reliable data	
		17.J Further develop measurements of progress	

As the introduction of biobased systems in companies plays a crucial role in achieving the SDGs, we have established the correlation between the principles and criteria of D1.2 with the SDGs and their targets, to evaluate the sustainability of biobased products with respect to these SDG targets. The relationship between these sustainable concepts will help us identify the most relevant set of targets in the SDGs to analyse biobased systems. The most relevant SDG objectives and targets addressed by the sustainability dimensions collected for biobased products were identified through this analysis and presented in section 3.1. These identified SDG targets will be used in the analysis of relationships to see which SDG targets show synergies, trade-offs or no direct relationship (presented in section 3.2 and in Annex Table 6).

2.2 Methodology followed to select representative bio-based value chains as example for each sector

The relevance of the six main European industrial sectors of interest for biobased products: chemical, construction, plastics, textile, woodworking, and pulp & paper, is a result of their large market size and value (ranging from 59 million to 1.6 billion euros)⁶, and the fact that a wide variety of essential products are derived from them, being thus relevant for industrial biobased systems. This includes personal care and homecare products, solvents and lubricants, consumer goods and packaging, flooring and building envelopes, clothing and sanitary products, among others.

In order to be able to analyse the sectors in more depth and with real data, representative bio-based value chains were selected as examples from each sector. A total of 25 biobased value chains were selected as example, with three to five value chains from each of the 6 sectors. These bio-based value chains serve as examples for carrying out the synergy and trade-off analysis and are not linked with the most representative biobased value chains selection that is carried out in Task 2.1 following the analytical hierarchy process. The selection of the representative value chains was specific, i.e., from a specific biological resource to a specific biobased product. The existence of sustainability certification schemes (either in terms of feedstock or final product, or as an ecolabel) was as well taken into consideration. Furthermore, to add another dimension to this study, novel promising technologies were included to the list. The idea was to evaluate emerging value chains (e.g., fibres from recycled textiles and microfibrillated cellulosic materials) besides the traditional ones, (e.g., cotton for textiles and mechanical pulp). Such technologies are considered innovative either in terms of using new feedstocks (e.g., organic wastes), being more efficient in water/energy usage, promoting circularity, and bringing new conversion processes able to unlock high-value markets from biological resources so far inaccessible. While many product possibilities derived from these novel processes are not yet available in a large industrial scale due to the challenges inherent to the development of new technologies (e.g., technical, regulatory, financial), their TRLs are high (>7) and they show a high demand, market push, and support from governments, society, and established industrial players that need to transition to more sustainable value chains.⁷⁻¹⁵

2.3 Methodology followed to analyse synergies and trade-offs

After selecting the representative biobased value chains (25) and SDG targets (85) using the methodologies described in the previous sections, a qualitative analysis was conducted to correlate each value chain with all SDG targets. The identified synergies were marked as positive (+), while trade-offs were marked as negative (-). Furthermore, a few that showed no strong synergy or trade-off (marked as +/-) were identified in the analysis, which refer to cases that can have both a positive

and negative correlation. As an example, for the SDG target related to the release of hazardous chemicals, while representative biobased value chains can prevent hazardous chemicals and pollution coming from petroleum sourcing and processing, most production processes for biomass and biobased chemicals use reagents that are hazardous (e.g. pesticides in cultivation, strong acids and other potential toxic or carcinogenic chemicals in processing). Only an in-depth analysis considering each specific product and chemical transformations could precisely indicate an overall positive or negative correlation (compared to a petro-based benchmark). As this is out of the scope of this report, which aimed at a more general overview, it was decided to use the +/- mark in such minor cases identified throughout the study. Finally, whenever a direct correlation could not be identified or no data was available, a non-applicable (na) mark was used. The qualitative scores were defined based on information and official data available online, such as technical reports from the European Commission, peer-reviewed academic literature, published life cycle analyses (LCAs) of relevant stakeholders, news articles, and experts' opinions.

Next, the obtained qualitative marks were converted to numeric values by applying a simple points system where positive marks were assigned with a +1 value, negative marks were assigned with a -1 value, and both +/- and non-applicable (na) marks were assigned with a value of 0 (zero). This simple system enabled getting a final "score" per value chain and was implemented to facilitate the overview of results (both per sector and per value chain), readability, and discussion. Furthermore, as the number of SDG targets considered applicable (i.e., received a qualitative assessment) varied per value chain, a normalisation step was added to enable the direct comparison between them, as well as their ranking.

The following equations were used to obtain the numerical scores reported in the results section. While equations (1)-(4) use the assigned numerical values as input to calculate a score (per value chain or per sector), equations (5)-(6) use the number of targets marked as positive, negative, or +/- as input to calculate averaged (per sector) numbers of applicable targets, as well as their percentage of synergies.

$$(1) \text{ Score per value chain} = \text{Sum(negative)} + \text{Sum(positive)}$$

$$(2) \text{ Score per sector} = \frac{\text{Sum(score per value chain)}}{\text{Amount of value chains per sector}}$$

$$(3) \text{ Normalised score per sector} = \frac{\text{Score per sector}}{\text{Number of applicable targets per sector}} \cdot 100$$

$$(4) \text{ Normalised score per value chain} = \frac{\text{Score per value chain}}{\text{Number of applicable targets per value chain}} \cdot 100$$

$$(5) \text{ Applicable targets per sector} = \frac{\text{Number of targets marked as (+) (-) (\pm)}}{\text{Number of value chains per sector}}$$

$$(6) \% \text{ Positive per value chain or sector} = \frac{\text{Number of targets marked as (+)}}{\text{Number of applicable targets}} \cdot 100$$

3. Results

3.1 Mapping the SDGs against sustainability dimensions

Based on the description of the SDGs and their respective targets described in section above, they were matched with the sustainability principles and criteria for biobased products shown in Table 1. This resulted in the identification of the SDG targets that are most relevant for industrial biobased systems. This matching exercise is presented as a matrix in Table 5 (Annex) and the results are detailed in Table 3. The 17 SDGs comprise a total of 169 targets, of which from the matching 85 were identified to be most relevant for analysing sustainability of biobased products. It is important to note that the principles and criteria are based on biobased systems and products, therefore, the relationships with the SDGs will be studied in the context of the biobased economy.

Table 3. SDG targets matched with each of the sustainability principle and criteria of biobased systems.

	Principle	Criteria	Correspondence to SDGs and targets
ENVIRONMENTAL	Reduce GHG emissions	Lifecycle GHG emissions	<p>Goal 9. Industry and infrastructure</p> <p>Target 13.2 Integrate climate change measures into national policies, strategies and planning.</p>
	Conserve land with high carbon stock and peatland	Protection of land with high carbon stock	<p>Goal 15. Life of land</p> <p>Target 15.1 Conserve and restore terrestrial and freshwater ecosystem. By 2020, ensure the conservation, restoration and sustainable use of terrestrial and inland freshwater ecosystems and their services, in particular forests, wetlands, mountains and drylands, in line with obligations under international agreement.</p>

		<p>Target 15.2 End deforestation and restore degraded forests. By 2020, promote the implementation of sustainable management of all types of forests, halt deforestation, restore degraded forests and substantially increase afforestation and reforestation globally.</p>
	Protection of peatland	<p>Goal 6. Clear water and sanitation</p> <p>Target 15.1 Conserve and restore terrestrial and freshwater ecosystem.</p> <p>Target 15.5 Protect biodiversity and natural habitats. Take urgent and significant action to reduce the degradation of natural habitats, halt the loss of biodiversity and, by 2020, protect and prevent the extinction of threatened species.</p>
Promote sustainable forest management	Maintaining forest productivity	<p>Goal 15. Life of land</p> <p>Target 15.2 End deforestation and restore degraded forests.</p> <p>Target 15.B Finance and incentivize forest management. Mobilize significant resources from all sources and at all levels to finance sustainable forest management and provide adequate incentives to developing countries to advance such management, including for conservation and reforestation.</p>
Promote the positive and reduce the negative impacts on ecosystems and biodiversity	Protection of land with a high biodiversity value	<p>Goal 14. Life below water</p> <p>Target 15.1 Conserve and restore terrestrial and freshwater ecosystem.</p> <p>Target 15.5 Protect biodiversity and natural habitats.</p>
	Restoration, preservation and strengthening of biodiversity	<p>Goal 2. Zero hunger</p> <p>Target 2.5 Maintain the genetic diversity in food production. By 2020 maintain genetic diversity of seeds, cultivated plants, farmed and</p>

			<p>domesticated animals and their related wild species, including through soundly managed and diversified seed and plant banks at national, regional and international levels, and ensure access to and fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from the utilization of genetic resources and associated traditional knowledge as internationally agreed.</p> <p>Goal 14. Life below water</p> <p>Target 15.1 Conserve and restore terrestrial and freshwater ecosystem.</p> <p>Target 15.5 Protect biodiversity and natural habitats.</p> <p>Target 15.8 Prevent invasive alien species on land. By 2020, introduce measures to prevent the introduction and significantly reduce the impact of invasive alien species on land and water ecosystems and control or eradicate the priority species.</p> <p>Target 15.A Increase financial resources to conserve and sustainably use ecosystem and biodiversity. Mobilize and significantly increase financial resources from all sources to conserve and sustainably use biodiversity and ecosystems.</p>
Conserve and protect water resources	Sustainable use of water		<p>Goal 6. Clear water and sanitation</p> <p>Target 6.4 Increase water-use efficiency and ensure freshwater supplies. By 2030, substantially increase water-use efficiency across all sectors and ensure sustainable withdrawals and supply of freshwater to address water scarcity, and substantially reduce the number of people suffering from water scarcity.</p> <p>Target 6.5 Implement integrated water resources management. By 2030 implement integrated water resources management at all levels, including through transboundary cooperation as appropriate.</p>
	Maintaining and enhancing water quality		<p>Goal 6. Clear water and sanitation</p> <p>Target 14.1 Reduce marine pollution. By 2025, prevent and significantly reduce marine pollution of all kinds, in particular from land-based activities, including marine debris and nutrient pollution.</p>

			<p>Target 14.3 Reduce Ocean acidification. Minimize and address the impacts of ocean acidification, including through enhanced scientific cooperation at all levels.</p>
Protect soil quality and productivity	Maintaining and enhancing soil quality		<p>Goal 2. Zero hunger</p> <p>Target 15.3 End desertification and restore degraded land. By 2030, combat desertification, restore degraded land and soil, including land affected by desertification, drought and floods, and strive to achieve a land degradation neutral world.</p>
	Use of residual flows		<p>Goal 12. Responsible consumption and production</p> <p>Target 12.5 Substantially reduce waste generation. By 2030, substantially reduce waste generation through prevention, reduction, recycling and reuse.</p>
Implement best practices for the use of (agro)chemicals	Prohibition on the use of hazardous/toxic chemicals		<p>Goal 3. Good health and well-being</p> <p>Target 3.9 Reduce illnesses and death from hazardous chemicals and pollution. By 2030 substantially reduce the number of deaths and illnesses from hazardous chemicals and air, water, and soil pollution and contamination.</p>
	Use, storage, handling and disposal of (agro)chemicals		<p>Goal 12. Responsible consumption and production</p> <p>Target 12.4 Responsible management of chemicals and waste. By 2020, achieve the environmentally sound management of chemicals and all wastes throughout their life cycle, in accordance with agreed international frameworks, and significantly reduce their release to air, water and soil in order to minimize their adverse impacts on human health and the environment.</p>
Restrict air pollution, promote good air quality	Air quality		<p>Goal 11. Sustainable cities and communities</p>

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			<p>Target 11.6 Reduce the environmental impact of cities. By 2030, reduce the adverse per capita environmental impact of cities, including by paying special attention to air quality and municipal and other waste management.</p>
		Restriction on open-air burning	
	Limit the risk of Indirect Land Use Change	ILUC Low Risk	<p>Goal 15. Life of land</p> <p>Target 15.2 End deforestation and restore degraded forests.</p>
CIRCULARITY	Promote responsible waste management	Waste management	<p>Goal 11. Sustainable cities and communities</p> <p>Target 12.4 Responsible management of chemicals and waste.</p> <p>Target 12.5 Substantially reduce waste generation.</p>
		Valorisation of residual flows	<p>Goal 8. Decent work and economic growth</p> <p>Target 12.3 Responsible management of chemicals and waste. By 2030, halve per capita global food waste at the retail and consumer levels and reduce food losses along production and supply chains, including post-harvest losses.</p> <p>Target 12.5 Substantially reduce waste generation.</p>
	Promote efficient use of energy and material resources	Raw material efficiency	<p>Goal 8. Decent work and economic growth</p>

			<p>Target 11.B Implement policies for inclusion resource efficiency and disaster risk reduction.</p> <p>Goal 12. Responsible consumption and production</p> <p>Target 12.2 Sustainable management and use of natural resources. By 2030, achieve the sustainable management and efficient use of natural resources.</p>
		Efficient use of energy	<p>Goal 7. Affordable and clean energy</p> <p>Target 7.3 Double the improvement in energy efficiency. Double the global rate of improvement in energy efficiency by 2030.</p> <p>Target 7.4 Promote access to research, technology and investments in clean energy. By 2030 enhance international cooperation to facilitate access to clean energy research and technologies, including renewable energy, energy efficiency, and advanced and cleaner fossil fuel technologies, and promote investment in energy infrastructure and clean energy technologies.</p>
		Use of renewable and non-renewable sources	<p>Goal 7. Affordable and clean energy</p> <p>Target 7.2 Increase substantially the share of renewable energy in the global energy mix by 2030.</p> <p>Target 7.5 Expand and upgrade energy services for developing countries. By 2030 expand infrastructure and upgrade technology for supplying modern and sustainable energy services for all in developing countries, particularly LDCs and SIDS.</p>
	Promote material circularity	Material circularity	<p>Goal 12. Responsible consumption and production</p> <p>Target 12.5 Substantially reduce waste generation.</p>
SOCIAL	Labour rights	Child labour	<p>Goal 4. Responsible consumption and production</p> <p>Target 8.7 End modern slavery, trafficking and child labour. Take immediate and effective measures to eradicate forced labour, end modern slavery and human trafficking and secure the prohibition and elimination of the worst forms of child labour, including recruitment and use of child soldiers, and by 2025 end child labour in all its forms.</p>

			<p>Goal 16. Peace, justice and institutions</p> <p>Target 16.2 Protect children from abuse, exploitation, trafficking and violence. Significantly reduce all forms of violence and related death rates everywhere.</p>
		Forced and compulsory labour	<p>Goal 8. Decent work and economic growth</p> <p>Target 8.7 End modern slavery, trafficking and child labour.</p> <p>Target 8.8 Protect labour rights and promote safe working environments. Protect labour rights and promote safe and secure working environments for all workers, including migrant workers, in particular women migrants, and those in precarious employment.</p>
		Fair salary, Remuneration	<p>Goal 8. Decent work and economic growth</p> <p>Target 8.5 Full employment and decent work with equal pay. By 2030, achieve full and productive employment and decent work for all women and men, including for young people and persons with disabilities, and equal pay for work of equal value.</p>
		Association and collective bargaining rights	<p>Goal 8. Decent work and economic growth</p> <p>Target 16.C Promote and enforce non-discriminatory laws and policies. Promote and enforce non-discriminatory laws and policies for sustainable development.</p>
		Equal opportunities/discrimination	<p>Goal 5. Gender equality</p> <p>Target 8.5 Full employment and decent work with equal pay.</p>

			<p>Goal 10. Reduced inequalities</p> <p>Target 10.3 Ensure equal opportunities and end discrimination. Ensure equal opportunity and reduce inequalities of outcome, including by eliminating discriminatory laws, policies and practices and promoting appropriate legislation, policies and action in this regard.</p> <p>Target 10.4 Adopt fiscal and social policies that promote equality. Adopt policies, especially fiscal, wage and social protection policies, and progressively achieve greater equality.</p>
		Grievance mechanism	<p>Goal 8. Decent work and economic growth</p> <p>Target 16.3 Promote the rule of law and ensure equal access to justice. Promote the rule of law at the national and international levels and ensure equal access to justice for all.</p>
Working conditions		Contract	<p>Goal 8. Decent work and economic growth</p> <p>Target 8.5 Full employment and decent work with equal pay.</p>
		Training	<p>Goal 8. Decent work and economic growth</p> <p>Target 8.6 Promote youth employment, education and training. By 2020, substantially reduce the proportion of youth not in employment, education or training A/RES/70/1 Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development 20/35.</p>
		Occupational health and safety	<p>Goal 8. Decent work and economic growth</p> <p>Target 8.8 Protect labour rights and promote safe working environments.</p>
		Harassment, violence	<p>Goal 5. Gender equality</p> <p>Target 5.2 End all violence against and exploitation of women and girls. By 2030, eliminate all forms of violence against all women and girls in public and private spheres, including trafficking and sexual and other types of exploitation.</p> <p>Goal 10. Reduced inequalities</p>

		<p>Target 16.1 Reduce violence everywhere. Significantly reduce all forms of violence and related death rates everywhere.</p> <p>Target 16.B Strengthen national institutions to prevent violence and combat terrorism and crime. Strengthen relevant national institutions, including through international cooperation, for building capacity at all levels, in particular in developing countries, to prevent violence and combat terrorism and crime.</p>
	Hours of work and overtime	
Property and usage rights	Land use rights (including land tenure)	<p>Goal 1. No poverty</p> <p>Target 5.7 Equal rights to economic resources, property ownership and financial services. By 2030, undertake reforms to give women equal rights to economic resources, as well as access to ownership and control over land and other forms of property, financial services, inheritance, and natural resources in accordance with national laws.</p>
	Water use rights	<p>Goal 1. No poverty</p> <p>Target 1.4 Equal rights to ownership, basic services, technology, and economic resources.</p>

		<p>Health and safety of local community</p>	<p>Goal 2. Zero hunger</p> <p>Target 12.4 Responsible management of chemicals and waste.</p>
	<p>Wellbeing of the local population</p>	<p>Local services (health, education, infrastructure, ...) / Prosperity</p>	<p>Goal 1. No poverty</p> <p>Target 6.2 End open defecation and provide access to sanitation and hygiene. By 2030, achieve access to adequate and equitable sanitation and hygiene for all, and end open defecation, paying special attention to the needs of women and girls and those in vulnerable situations.</p> <p>Goal 7. Affordable and clean energy</p>

		<p>Target 11.1 Safe and affordable housing. By 2030, ensure access for all to adequate, safe and affordable housing and basic services and upgrade slums.</p> <p>Target 11.2 Affordable and sustainable transport systems. By 2030, provide access to safe, affordable, accessible and sustainable transport systems for all, improving road safety, notably by expanding public transport, with special attention to the needs of those in vulnerable situations, women, children, persons with disabilities and older persons.</p>	
	Local values		<p>Goal 11. Sustainable cities and communities</p> <p>Target 11.4 Protect the world’s cultural and natural heritage. Strengthen efforts to protect and safeguard the world’s cultural and natural heritage.</p>
	Community involvement		<p>Goal 6. Clear water and sanitation</p> <p>Target 16.7 Ensure responsive, inclusive, and representative decision-making. Ensure responsive, inclusive, participatory and representative decision-making at all levels.</p>
	Food security		<p>Goal 2. Zero hunger</p>

			<p>Target 2.1 Universal access to safe and nutritious food. By 2030 end hunger and ensure access by all people, in particular the poor and people in vulnerable situations including infants, to safe, nutritious and sufficient food all year round.</p> <p>Target 2.C Ensure stable food commodity markets and timely access to information. Adopt measures to ensure the proper functioning of food commodity markets and their derivatives, and facilitate timely access to market information, including on food reserves, in order to help limit extreme food price volatility.</p>
<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">ECONOMIC</p>	<p>Financial and economic viability (Economic sustainability, continual improvement)</p>		<p>Goal 8. Decent work and economic growth</p> <p>Target 14.7 Increase the economic benefits from sustainable use of marine resources. By 2030, increase the economic benefits to small island developing States and least developed countries from the sustainable use of marine resources, including through sustainable management of fisheries, aquaculture and tourism.</p>
	<p>Fair business practices, Integrity (fraudulent, deceptive, or dishonest)</p>		<p>Goal 15. Life of land</p> <p>Target 16.5 Substantially reduce corruption and bribery. Substantially reduce corruption and bribery in all their forms.</p> <p>Target 16.6 Develop effective, accountable, and transparent institutions. Develop effective, accountable and transparent institutions at all levels.</p>

	Inclusive economic growth	Local employment and procurement	<p>Goal 2. Zero hunger</p> <p>Target 9.1 Develop sustainable, resilient, and inclusive infrastructures.</p>
		Community investment	<p>Goal 4. Responsible consumption and production</p> <p>Target 9.8 Universal Access to information and communications technology. Significantly increase access to information and communications technology and strive to provide universal and affordable access to the Internet in least developed countries by 2020.</p>
	Compensate indigenous knowledge		
Use of knowledge and technology		Use of technology	<p>Goal 2. Zero hunger</p> <p>Target 2.A Invest in rural infrastructure, agricultural research, technology, and gene banks. Increase investment, including through enhanced international cooperation, in rural infrastructure, agricultural research and</p>

			<p>extension services, technology development, and plant and livestock gene banks to enhance agricultural productive capacity in developing countries, in particular in least developed countries.</p> <p>Goal 9. Industry and infrastructure</p> <p>Target 17.7 Promote sustainable technologies to developing countries. Promote the development, transfer, dissemination and diffusion of environmentally sound technologies to developing countries on favourable terms, including on concessional and preferential terms, as mutually agreed.</p>
	<p>Fair trade and market practices</p>		<p>Goal 2. Zero hunger</p> <p>Target 8.B Increase aid for trade support. By 2020, develop and operationalize a global strategy for youth employment and implement the Global Jobs Pact of the International Labour Organization.</p>

			<p>Goal 9. Industry and infrastructure</p> <p>Target 17.A Promote a universal trading system under the WTO. Promote a universal, rules-based, open, non-discriminatory and equitable multilateral trading system under the World Trade Organization, including through the conclusion of negotiations under its Doha Development Agenda.</p> <p>Target 17.C Remove trade barriers for least developed countries. Realize timely implementation of duty-free, quota-free market access on a lasting basis for all least developed countries consistent with WTO decisions, including through ensuring that preferential rules of origin applicable to imports from LDCs are transparent and simple, and contribute to facilitating market access.</p>
	<p>Risk assessment and management</p>		

For some of the sustainability criteria no SDG target was found that explicitly addresses that aspect. These are “restriction on open-air burning” (environmental dimension), “hours of work and overtime” (social dimension), “compensate indigenous knowledge” and “risk assessment and management” (economic dimension).

The matching based on bibliographic references¹⁶⁻¹⁹ and the description of the different targets, have resulted in some targets to be repeated linked to different sustainability principles, such as the case of target “12.4 Responsible management of chemicals and waste” of SDG 12, “Responsible consumption and production”, which was matched with criteria within the environmental, circularity and social dimensions. Whereas some of the targets were repeated in several of the sustainability criteria within a certain dimension e.g., target “15.1 Conserve and restore terrestrial and freshwater ecosystem” of SDG 15, “Life on Land” was matched with several of the criteria in environmental dimension and target “8.8 Protect labour rights and promote safe working environments” of SDG 8 “Decent work and economic growth” was matched with several of the criteria in social dimension.

The percentage coverage of the targets from each SDG from the matching with the sustainability criteria for biobased products are shown in Figure 3. Further break down of the matching of SDG targets with sustainability criteria for each dimension is shown in Figure 4. Please note that the total of the numbers in Figure 5 does not match with Figure 4 because of the repetition of some of the SDG targets in several sustainability dimensions.

Figure 3. Percentage of targets of each SDG matched with sustainability criteria of biobased systems.

All SDG targets are related to sustainability dimensions to some extent, varying in degree. It is seen that SDGs 2 and 7 have all their targets matched to criteria, while SDGs 4 and 17 have the lowest coverage with 14% and 16%, respectively. Specifically, only one out of the 7 targets that make up SDG 1 was matched, which is "1.4 Equal rights to ownership, basic services, technology, and economic resources" that was matched with criteria within the social dimension. In the case of SDG 17, only 3 out of the 19 targets are matched with the sustainability criteria, specifically within the economic dimension. It is also seen that some of the SDGs are predominantly linked to one of the sustainability dimensions such as SDG 5 Gender equality to social dimension, and SDG 13 Climate action to environmental dimension. Whereas some other SDGs are linked to several dimensions

such as SDG 2 “zero hunger”, 11 “sustainable cities and communities” and 12 “responsible consumption and production” (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Percentage of targets of each SDG matched with sustainability criteria of biobased systems broken down into 4 dimensions.

Figures 5 to 8 provide more details on the matching with SDG targets per sustainability dimension.

Environmental dimension

Figure 5. Graph of the relationship between each SDG with the environmental dimension.

SDG 15, "Life on land", focuses on protecting, restoring, and promoting the sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, biodiversity, and the ecosystem services they provide. Therefore, most of its goals and targets are directly related to the environmental dimension of sustainability. For example, some of its goals include halting deforestation and desertification, conserving and restoring terrestrial ecosystems, protecting biodiversity and habitats of endangered species, and promoting sustainable agricultural and forestry practices. Due to this concentration on environmental issues, SDG 15 has the highest contribution to the environmental dimension of sustainability (Figure 5).

Likewise, SDG 14, "Life below water", focuses on conserving and sustainably using oceans, seas, and marine resources for sustainable development. Therefore, most of its objectives and targets are directly related to the environmental dimension of sustainability. For example, some of its goals include preventing and reducing marine pollution, protecting and restoring marine and coastal ecosystems, and regulating fishing to achieve long-term sustainability of marine resources.

SDG 6 "Clean water and sanitation" also has important contribution to the environmental dimension of sustainability. This SDG focuses on ensuring universal and equitable access to safe and adequate water, sanitation, and hygiene for all, and improving the quality of water and sustainable management of water resources. Sustainable water management and improving water quality directly contribute to the conservation and protection of aquatic ecosystems and associated biodiversity. Therefore, SDG 6 is also involved in the environmental dimension of sustainability.

There are goals that should be closely related to the environmental dimension, but low coverage was seen i.e., SDG 13 "Climate action" may seem to have a strong relationship with the environmental dimension, it was hard to find a matching target. This is because the targets established in this objective aim to integrate the climate change into national policies and strategies,

improvement of education and awareness about climate change, mobilization of funding for climate action and promotion of adaptation to the impacts of climate change in vulnerable communities.

On the other hand, there are goals that may seem unrelated to the environmental dimension but were found to have linkages. For example, SDG 3, "Good health and well-being", focuses on ensuring healthy lives and promoting well-being for all ages, which indirectly relates to the environmental dimension because the environment directly affects human health. Environmental degradation can pose serious health risks such as respiratory, infectious, and chronic diseases. Achieving the goals of SDG 3 can contribute to the conservation and protection of the environment and to reducing health risks. The promotion of healthy practices and behaviours can also have a positive impact on environmental sustainability.

No specific linkage was found with the targets of SDGs 1, 4, 5, 7, 8, 10, 16, and 17 and the environmental dimension of sustainability. These SDGs do not have a direct relationship with the environmental dimension of sustainability because their objectives and targets focus on other aspects of sustainability.

Circularity dimension

Figure 6. Graph of the relationship between each SDG with the circularity dimension.

The SDGs 7, 8, 11, and 12 are related to circularity because they focus on promoting practices and strategies that encourage resource efficiency, waste reduction, and reuse and recycling of materials (Figure 6). They focus on sustainable economic growth, the use of renewable energy sources, the sustainable planning and management of human settlements, and responsible consumption and production. The implementation of circular economy practices can contribute to the reduction of waste and greenhouse gas emissions and promote environmental sustainability.

SDG 7, "Affordable and clean energy," aims to promote the transition to renewable energy sources and increase energy efficiency in all sectors, which implies reducing greenhouse gas emissions and efficiently using energy resources. The implementation of renewable energies, such as solar and

wind energy, can contribute to circularity by reducing the dependence on non-renewable fossil fuels. This is also important for industrial biobased systems where in their production also energy is needed which should also be supplied from renewable sources.

SDG 12 "Responsible consumption and production," which emphasizes the promotion of sustainable practices in the production and consumption of goods and services, has a focus on efficient management of natural resources, responsible management of waste, waste reduction, and circular economy promotion.

Also, a linkage was seen with the SDG 8, "Decent work and economic growth", related to the target 8.4 "Improve resource efficiency in consumption and production" and with the SDG 11 "Sustainable cities and communities" related to targets on waste management and resource efficiency.

Social dimension

Figure 7. Graph of the relationship between each SDG with the social dimension.

The SDGs have a strong social dimension (Figure 7), as they aim to achieve a better and more sustainable future for all people. The 17 SDGs cover a wide range of social issues, such as poverty reduction, gender equality, health and well-being, education, and sustainable cities and communities. The social dimension of the SDGs is reflected in the fact that they were developed based on extensive consultations and input from a wide range of stakeholders, including civil society organizations, academia, and the private sector. The SDGs prioritize the needs of people and communities and seek to ensure that no one is left behind in the pursuit of sustainable development.

The most relevant relationships have been found in SDG 16, SDG 8, and SDG 2. SDG 16 "Peace, justice and institutions" relates to the social dimension by addressing fundamental challenges related to justice and equal access to human rights such as reducing violence, protecting children, non-

discrimination, inclusive decision making, which are essential for building more inclusive and just societies. SDG 8, “Decent work and economic growth” addresses the social dimension by focusing on job creation and decent work for all, which is especially linked to the social principles on labour rights and working conditions of employees. SDG 2 “Zero hunger” has a target on equal rights to ownership which is relevant for land use and water use rights and is also linked to prosperity of local communities.

However, there are SDGs with goals not related to social dimensions, such as goals 13 “Climate action”, 14 “Life below water”, 15 “Life of land” and 17 “Partnership for the goals”.

Economic dimension

Figure 8. Graph of the relationship between each SDG with the economic dimension.

The relationship between the SDGs and the economic dimension is fundamental, as most SDGs have an economic dimension that implies a transformation of current economic models towards more sustainable ones. That is why majority of SDGs have a contribution in Figure 8.

Highest relationship was seen for SDG 8 and 9. SDG 8, “Decent work and economic growth” which aims to promote sustained, inclusive, and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment, and decent work for all, is particularly relevant to the economic dimension of the bioeconomy. The SDG 8 targets were closely linked to the criteria on economic viability and job creation. The bioeconomy can provide opportunities for economic growth through the development of new markets, the creation of jobs, and the stimulation of innovation. SDG 9 “Industry and infrastructure” is particularly relevant as it promotes the development of sustainable industrial processes and infrastructure that use renewable resources. This can be achieved through investments in research and development, support technology development, access to financial services and markets, and development of sustainable supply chains. By aligning with SDG 9, the

biobased economy can contribute to sustainable economic growth and the achievement of the broader SDGs.

SDGs 2 and 14 were also found relevant for economic dimension. SDG 2 “zero hunger” has targets related to the productivity and income of farmers, investment in rural infrastructure and preventing market restrictions which are closely linked to the economic principles of biobased systems. SDG 14 “life below water” has targets on increasing the economic benefits from sustainable use of marine resources and increasing research and development which is relevant for the economic development of biobased systems.

There are also SDGs with lower relations is seen such as SDG 15, “Life of land” and SDG 10, “Reduced inequalities” which are more linked to other sustainability dimensions of environment and social.

3.2 Qualitative analysis of the representative biobased value chains actions with respect to SDG targets

By applying the methodology described in Section 2.2., a total of 25 biobased value chains were selected as example, with three to five value chains from each of the 6 sectors. Their general description is presented in Table 4. As noted above this selection is separate to the identification of the most representative biobased value chains that is carried out in Task 2.1 and serve as input for trade flow and cost benefit analysis carried out in the project.

Table 4. General description of the representative biobased value chains selected for each sector as an example for synergy and trade-off analysis.

Sector	No	Value chain	Feedstock	Feedstock classification (D1.1.)	General comments
CHEMICALS	1	Novel and drop-in chemical building blocks (e.g. ethylene, succinic acid, lactic acid)	Sugar and starch crops	Primary dedicated	Used as building blocks to produce a range of chemicals and materials, replacement of fossil-based chemicals
	2	Novel and drop-in chemical building blocks (e.g. dicarboxylic acids, glycols, diols)	Sugars from lignocellulosic residues e.g., wheat straw	Primary and secondary plant residues from agriculture and forestry	
	3	Novel resins from forest residues	Tall oil, lignin, tannins	Primary and secondary residues, Residues from forest industry	Replacement of fossil-based chemicals in adhesives, coatings, and paints for various applications
	4	Oleochemicals (e.g. fatty acids, fatty acids esters, fatty alcohols and glycerine)	Animal fat waste, used cooking oil, wastes from	Secondary residues from agri-food industry and meat processing industry, tertiary residues and wastes	Replacement of fossil-based chemicals used in lubricants, surfactants, use as chemical building blocks

			vegetable oils processing		and in cosmetic formulations
	5	Oleochemicals (e.g. fatty acids, fatty acids esters, fatty alcohols and glycerine)	Oil crops, e.g., palm, soy, rapeseed	Primary dedicated	
	6	Fine chemicals (e.g., vanillin, geraniol, cinnamic acid, geranyl acetate, linalool)	Biobased sources, e.g. flowers, leaves, vanillin from lignin	Primary dedicated, primary residues	Replacement of petro-based chemicals used in high-value industries such as fragrance and flavour and cosmetics
CONSTRUCTION	1	Rigid polyurethane foams (rPUs)	Lignin, tall oil, hemicelluloses	Secondary residues, residues from forest industry	Replacement of petro-based polyols in rPUs, which are used for insulation in roofing and flooring
	2	Fibreboards and concrete	Hemp	Primary dedicated	Replacement of energy intensive, inorganic materials (aluminium, steel, concrete) with natural materials, upcycling side streams
	3	Oriented strand board	Lignocellulosic residues e.g., wheat straw	Primary and secondary plant residues from agriculture and forestry	
	4	Wood-based particleboards for interior construction	Wood residues	Primary residues from forestry	
PLASTICS	1	Polypropylene (PP)	Used cooking oil	Tertiary residues and wastes	Replacement of PP made of petro-based propylene
	2	Polyethylene (PE) and ethylene vinyl acetate (EVA) using green ethylene, Polylactic acid (PLA)	Sugar crops	Primary dedicated, primary plant residues	Replacement of PE and EVA made from petro-based ethylene, PLA as a more environmentally friendly packaging solution
	3	Novel composites and thermoplastic materials from waste	Forestry wastes, municipal wastes	Secondary and tertiary residues and wastes	Replacement of both single-use and durable plastics, adhesives or thin coatings used in paper and cardboard
	4	Bioplastics using biological metabolism (such as PHA)	Organic waste, wastewater	Tertiary residues and wastes	Replacement of plastics from petrol to PHA produced by bacteria
TEX TILE	1	Cotton textile value chain	Cotton	Primary dedicated	Traditional industry

	2	Recycling cotton and other cellulose-rich textiles, novel efficient spinning technologies	New and used textile fibres	Primary dedicated, tertiary residues and wastes	Water-based chemical processes (no harmful chemicals) able to recycle cellulose-rich textiles into new yarns of high quality, new spinning technologies that save water
	3	Textiles from other natural fibres	Flax, hemp	Primary dedicated	Textile fibres from other natural (agricultural) sources
	4	Cellulosic fibres (e.g., Lyocell, Viscose)	Wood	Primary dedicated	Traditional industry that can replace fossil-based fibres, such as polyesters and nylon.
WOODWORKING	1	Use of lignocellulosic residues for interiorism and decoration	Lignocellulosic resources e.g., wheat straw, hemp	Primary dedicated and (mostly) primary residues from agriculture and forestry	Replacing plastics and primary dedicated wood
	2	Particle boards for interior construction, carpentry pieces (cases, boxes, crates, drums, etc.)	Wood residues	Primary residues from forestry	Wood residues (particularly coniferous) as a replacement to durable plastics
	3	Use of sawdust and other subproducts in woodworking industry	Sawdust	Secondary residue from forestry	Substitute of primary dedicated wood by subproducts of wood industry
PULP&PAPER	1	Resistant packaging (cartons, boxes, and cases of corrugated paper) from mechanical or semi-chemical pulp	Wood	Primary dedicated	Traditional industry, uses wood (particularly coniferous), can replace plastics
	2	Paper for graphic purposes	Recycled paper	Tertiary residues or waste	Use (recycling) of paper wastes into new paper with artistic value
	3	Specialty cellulose, microfibrillated cellulose (MFCs), and micro-nano crystalline cellulose (MCCs, CNCs)	Wood	Primary dedicated mostly, but possible with primary residues from agriculture and forestry	Specialty cellulose is a traditional product with use in textiles, pharma, food, and cosmetic industries (e.g., viscose, cellulose ethers and acetate, nitrocellulose). MFCs and MCCs emerging cellulosic materials with potential ranging from cosmetics to batteries and coatings,

	4	Napkins, tissues, and food packaging	fibres from lignocellulosic sources e.g., sugarcane bagasse	Secondary plant residues from the agri-food industry	replacing inorganic and petro-based materials. Secondary residues to replace virgin wood and single use plastics
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For the qualitative analysis of each biobased value chain regarding the selected SDG targets, a thorough search was conducted for information and official data available online. This included technical reports from the European Commission, peer-reviewed academic literature, published life cycle analyses (LCAs) of relevant stakeholders, news articles, and experts' opinions. The identified synergies were marked as positive (+), while trade-offs were marked as negative (-). Furthermore, a few targets where no clear synergy or trade-off exist were marked as (+/-), and non-applicable targets were marked as (na). See Annex for the full table containing the results discussed below.

Depending on the target being evaluated, there was a larger focus on different characteristics of the value chain, such as the biobased feedstock origin and supply chain, the conversion processes, differences between stakeholders belonging to traditional or innovative technologies, low tech/high tech transformations, and EU dependency on importing/self-sufficiency. Figure 9 shows the total number of targets applicable per sector, and which proportion of those were synergic (positive). The first observation is that, in value chains with similar feedstocks (i.e., chemicals and plastics; construction and woodworking; and textiles and pulp & paper), a similar number of targets were considered applicable. Furthermore, in the sectors where value chains are relatively more forestry-based (construction and woodworking), less targets were considered applicable. This difference is mainly due to SDG targets related to food production (not directly applicable to forestry) and some targets linked to the social criterion. Accordingly, social issues are heavily reported in the cotton, sugar crops, and textile value chains^{20,21}, where Europe largely depends on importing, so they were taken into consideration and had a negative impact. On the other hand, these issues have a much lower weight when considering forest-based value chains, which are well-regulated in Europe and there is an overall self-sufficiency.²²

The proportion of synergies based in the number of applicable targets vary from 76%-89% depending on the sector, and these differences are related to the trade-offs of the different value chains included in each sector. The textiles and chemicals sectors scored the lowest, while construction and pulp & paper scored the highest. These results will be further detailed by zooming in into the value chains and using the normalised score as a more comprehensive and comparative metric. Accordingly, the score calculation takes into consideration the negative effect of trade-offs (by converting each negative mark into a numerical value of -1 that is subtracted from the sum of positives). A normalisation was necessary for a fair comparison between value chains, as a different number of targets were considered applicable in each value chain (similar as what is observed in the light green bars of Figure 9, which is plotted per sector). These parameters are defined in the methodology section 2.3.

Figure 9. Number of targets assessed per sector and percentage of synergies.

The normalised score of each value chain for all sectors is shown in Figure 10. For instance, a value of 100% means that all applicable targets of the value chain were assessed as positive, therefore the closest to 100%, the better in terms of sustainability dimensions. There is a marked difference between value chains (for the description of each of them, the reader is referred to Table 4) and sectors. Next, the results of each sector are discussed in detail, and the overall normalised score per sector is presented to conclude this section and support the main conclusions.

Figure 10. Normalised score per value chain in all evaluated sectors.

Chemicals sector

Figure 11. Normalised score per value chain in the chemical sector.

- The best value chain identified in this sector was the fourth, oleochemicals from waste (animal fats, used cooking oils and various wastes and residues from vegetable oils processing). In this case, the assessment was fully positive, as the valorisation of wastes brings in the circularity dimension much needed in current value chains, can increase the income of small-scale enterprises, reduce pollution and the environmental impact of cities, promote employment and a sustainable economic growth.²³ Accordingly, there is great support for the development of novel biorefinery concepts using waste as feedstock, even more when said biorefineries can leverage the feedstock potential to yield high value products. In this sense, various routes from UCOs (used cooking oils) from valuable chemicals (e.g. plasticizers, epoxies, polyols, lubricants, surfactants, among others) have been reported.^{24,25}
- Next, the value chain 3 (novel resins from forest residues) scored the highest (79%). This value chain has many benefits of waste valorisation, no competition with food, and replacement of petro-based macromolecules that tend to be resource intensive and polluting to produce. The various developments ongoing in the field of biobased resins (adhesives, coatings, etc) push for research and international cooperation.^{26,27} This field has been difficult to defossilize and recently gained much attention, with new technologies and projects that create jobs and infrastructures. An example is the ARC CBBC²⁸ research cluster, comprised of important actors of the chemical industry (BASF, AkzoNobel, Shell) and universities, with projects targeting biobased recyclable coatings made of new building blocks from renewable sources such as wood. The Lignicoat²⁹ project funded by EU aims to demonstrate technical and economic feasibility of the use of lignin as raw material to produce bio-resins for different applications in the field of functional and sustainable coatings. The main trade-offs are related to the facts that *i*) fully biobased resins are difficult to achieve and most current applications replace petro-based ingredients partially, and/or still use toxic compounds such as formaldehyde and polyamines to reach the required specifications; *ii*) even if fully biobased, the chemistry of resins is marked by non-biodegradability and non-recyclability due to its crosslinked and chemically heterogeneous structure, being a potential source of pollution, chemical leaching, and acidification. In this sense, new eco-design and efficient recycling approaches are fundamental to ensure the full sustainability of such products.³⁰
- For the value chain of fine chemicals (number 6, normalized score of 74%), synergies exist particularly when considering the use of residual biomass for obtaining valuable compounds. An

example is the extraction of ferulic acid (FA) from rice bran, one of the main by-products in the process of the rice milling. FA has very interesting properties (e.g., antioxidant, antimicrobial³¹), and can be converted into other valuable compounds such as vanillin (a route commercialized by Solvay³²). Another example targeting vanillin is the value chain owned by Borregaard, which produces vanillin from wood. An externally conducted LCA (life cycle analysis) showed a 90% reduction in CO₂ emissions for the process when compared to the impact of obtaining vanillin from fossil resources.^{33,34} Nowadays, the global and increasing vanillin demand (around 20'000 tons) is almost entirely (>85%) met by synthetic vanillin produced from petroleum-derived phenol³⁵. Hence, there is a high demand for biobased alternatives with great associated synergies. Nonetheless, possible trade-offs can be pointed from a more general analysis, for instance the toxicological profile and acidity of some biobased chemicals (e.g. phenols) that can lead to water acidification upon disposal.³⁶ Furthermore, concerns of overexploitation of natural resources are present in the fine chemicals value chains, which can be resource intensive, and require vast quantities of plant material, water, and land for a small yield of product.³⁷ For instance, in the fragrances industry, the supply chain intricacy makes it difficult for brands to monitor practices, which allows many of them to limit their accountability on issues related to endangered species and deforestation. The high value and demand of these natural molecules is responsible for overharvesting, particularly when they come from conflicting regions. An example is the perfumery ingredient *frankincense*, obtained exclusively from five tree species found mostly in Africa and the Middle East. Even though 50% of the wild *Boswellia* forests can disappear within the next years according to conservationists, an article that surveyed niche brands reported that some didn't know that the ingredient is threatened or couldn't even identify where their ingredients came from.³⁸ This clearly shows the issues on decentralized value chains without proper traceability and regulations, both from local governments and from the suppliers that intermediate the moving from farmers to perfume brands. Despite recent efforts and responsible sourcing policy documents issued by major brands such as Givaudan³⁹, this still happens in some niche biobased fine chemicals, being thus considered a trade-off.

- The value chain 2 scored 55% and refers to the conversion of sugars from lignocellulosic residues, particularly hemicelluloses, to novel and drop-in chemical building blocks (e.g. dicarboxylic acids and diols). Many technologies are on the rise due to the resource efficiency aspect of using a side stream as feedstock and the possibility of replacing molecules currently obtained from petroleum. For example, a novel potential replacement of terephthalic acid (monomer in PET plastic production) developed from hemicellulosic sources rich in xylose (e.g. corncobs) has a lower carbon footprint in all three scenarios considered in the LCA (20-85% lower).⁴⁰ These are clear synergies that go beyond environmental benefits, but also promote the development of infrastructures, entrepreneurship, and applied research. Nonetheless, trade-offs related to the use of toxic and corrosive reagents (e.g. strong acids) in the production processes remain, which can lead to release of hazardous chemicals. Furthermore, depending on the sugar crop type and origin, strong social issues might arise from the supply chain side. For instance, the sugarcane industry is, to date, marked by hostile conditions, unfair pay, human trafficking, and exploitation (particularly of women and children).⁴¹⁻⁴³
- The value chains 1 (chemical building blocks from sugar crops) and 5 (oleochemicals from palm, soy, rapeseed) had the worst scores (27-31%) of the sector, which the prevalence of trade-offs over synergies. This is a combination of the known strong social issues aforementioned⁴¹⁻⁴³, which are even stronger for the case of using primary dedicated crops (not residues). Accordingly, both the sugar and vegetable oils primary industries are linked to serious human exploitation and inefficiency (as these are value chains of lower technology), as well as to soil depletion due to intensive monoculture.^{44,45} Furthermore, these crops compete with food and can negatively impact the market by creating distortions and speculations. Deforestation and loss of

biodiversity can be another result from such high demand and pricing fluctuations.⁴⁶ Some advanced technologies enable the production of drop-in chemicals with lower associated CO₂ emissions, e.g. the company Avantium reported a carbon footprint cut of 56-85% of biobased monoethylene glycol (MEG) from fructose over fossil-based MEG⁴⁷, which is a positive aspect. However, the agricultural dependency of the technology drives the terrestrial eutrophication and land use impact in comparison to fossil technologies, which are environmental trade-offs.

Construction sector

Figure 12. Normalised score per value chain in the construction sector

- Overall, the value chains selected for the construction sector have a very good score due to being mostly based in the upcycling of side streams or in the development of sustainable solutions. The best value chain identified in this sector was the value chain 2, related to the production of fibreboard and concrete using hemp. The use of this feedstock in the construction sector has several advantages, such as the fast growth rate (6 months, compared to about 50 years for oak trees), competitive price, carbon sequestration (i.e. growing hemp stores 2 tons of CO₂ per acre) and non-toxicity. For instance, the so-called “hempcrete” is a biocomposite with great thermal insulation properties, used in non-bearing walls, as finishing plasters and floor/roof panels. It is primarily used as an insulation material rather than as a structural or load-bearing material, given its relatively lower strength due to the porous structure and lower water resistance. Nonetheless, the range of applications is wide and so is the popularity of this material. Besides the substantially lower footprint compared to typical concrete (an industry known for the extremely high energy usage and an estimated footprint of 0.9 ton CO₂/ton of concrete⁴⁸), research shows that additional carbon storage happens by carbonation of the hempcrete binder. Accordingly, the overall emission balance is very favourable: thanks to biogenic CO₂ uptake during hemp growth and to CO₂ uptake by carbonation, hempcrete blocks have a negative carbon footprint and act therefore as effective carbon sinks, sequestering ca. 16 kg of CO₂/m².^{49,50} In this context, all applicable targets were valued as positive, except for one trade-off on the SDG target 3.9, related to the release of hazardous chemicals and pollution, which was considered ambiguous. This ambiguity rises from the fibreboard value chain, in which resins are used to give mechanical properties to the material. Such resins (described in the previous chemicals section), still relies in toxic reagents and are typically non-biodegradable.

- The value chains 3 and 4 had a high score too (88-91%), being related to oriented strand board made from lignocellulosic residues (e.g. straw) and wood-based particle boards. The so-called OSSB (oriented structural straw board) uses formaldehyde-free resins and can replace wood-based oriented strand boards in structural and non-structural applications. The substitution of a primary source by an agricultural residue is very positive in terms of circularity, diversification of economic productivity and improving resource efficiency. While the use of a formaldehyde-free binder makes the material safer in terms of releasing toxic VOCs (volatile organic compounds), OSSB typically uses methylene diphenyl diisocyanate (p-MDI) as a binder, which is highly reactive respiratory tract and skin irritants. Without a proper engineering control, work practices and personal protective equipment, high exposure levels can occur.⁵¹ This was considered the only ambiguous point in the analysis of this value chain. For the wood-based particleboards, similar synergies (residue valorisation) and trade-offs (use of resins with issues related to non-biodegradability and reagents toxicity - in this case, formaldehyde⁵²) are identified. Despite being wood based, this material is mainly produced from residues, and therefore not considered to be detrimental in terms of deforestation.
- The value chain 1 is related to the use of a lignocellulosic residue, lignin, to produce rigid polyurethane foams (rPUs). These rigid foams are largely used as insulation panels in the construction sector, and lignin can potentially replace the fossil-based aromatic polyols currently used for this purpose.⁵³⁻⁵⁵ Lignin is a major by-product of pulp and paper industry and consists of a phenolic biopolymer with interesting properties (i.e. flame retardancy), low cost and abundance. It has therefore attracted interest for the development of sustainable materials, and many synergies can be identified. Beyond synergies in terms of waste valorisation, the development of such novel materials is backed up by research and technology advances, promoting education, jobs and infrastructure, and expanding possibilities from lignocellulosic biomass to higher-value applications.⁵⁶ Nonetheless, issues inherent to the chemistry of such materials (e.g. PUs and epoxies) can't be ignored, as the processes often use toxic reagents as hardeners and the final materials are not biodegradable and can cause pollution if not properly disposed and managed.

Plastics sector

Figure 13. Normalised score per value chain in the plastics sector.

- Within the plastics sector, the score varied substantially among the selected value chains, being an interesting result of the wide variety of feedstocks, processes and end products considered. The best score is seen for value chain number 4, which is related to novel types of bioplastics, particularly PHAs (polyhydroxyalkanoates), which are biocompatible, biobased and biodegradable polyesters produced in nature by bacterial fermentation of sugar and lipids. Organic waste streams (e.g. used cooking oils, sludges, organic fraction from municipal waste streams, paper wastes, etc) can be used to produce PHA, which makes this alternative extremely interesting due to avoiding pollution and converting complex streams into valuable materials.⁵⁷ Being still in relative infancy, technological challenges still need to be overcome and the market is small compared to other plastics. Nonetheless, the high demand and sustainability profile are currently pushing the PHAs applications and market, which is quickly growing from 57 million US\$ (2019), to 98 million US\$ (2021).⁵⁸ In terms of the selected SDG targets, the development of this type of material combines *i*) technological advances that promote jobs, infrastructure, research activities and international cooperation with *ii*) new possibilities for wastewater/sanitation management, the support for industrial diversification and the development of clean techs and SMEs; *iii*) the economic and social benefits for cooperatives and poor communities in a supply chain that valorises municipal waste; and *iv*) replacing petro-based, non-biodegradable plastics by a much more eco-friendly alternative.
 - The second high scored value chain was the number 3, related to the development of novel composites and thermoplastic materials from waste. Innovative concepts are gaining much attention due to their strong circularity cases that enable the valorisation of complex streams such as municipal wastes, sewage sludges, etc. A notable example is the UBQ Materials, a technology company offering a solution to the waste crisis. The process begins with mixed municipal solid waste that would have otherwise been sent to landfill or incineration. The waste, largely comprised of organic materials, is then converted into a composite thermoplastic material, and the process can be 100% powered by renewable energy. The final product has a wide range of applications such as automotive, construction, and retail, and it is reported that for every 1 ton of composite produced, 1.3 tons of waste are diverted from landfill, and up to 11.7 tons of CO₂ emissions are avoided.⁵⁹ Other developments aim at the production of healable materials, avoiding waste generation in the first place by extending the material lifetime.⁶⁰ Given these promising numbers and potential, there is a high interest and support for the scale-up and full implementation of such technologies.⁶¹ As such, synergies were prevalent when correlating these novel value chains with the selected SDG targets. The few trade-offs and ambiguous points identified are related to pollution – as these composites are not biodegradable, their management is important to bring them back to the circular value chain, as the wrong disposal will lead to environmental drawbacks and persisting pollutants.
 - The value chain 1 refers to the production of polypropylene (PP) from used cooking oils (UCOs), with a good score of 70%. Accordingly, the use of such tertiary wastes to replace a petro-based polymer with strong environmental concerns brings several benefits. Compared to petrochemical PP, UCO-PP is reported to bring substantial impact savings for climate change (62%) and fossil fuel resource use (86%).⁶² This "drop-in solution", i.e. the final materials (petro-PP and UCO-PP) are chemically the same, brings benefits of an easier implementation and adoption by industries and consumers, no extra regulatory bottlenecks and no technical challenges for moulding/extruding the polymer into final products. Furthermore, adding value to wastes will likely support new, decentralized actors, such as small enterprises on waste collection, pre-treatment and primary separation. A nice example is reported in the InnovOleum project, which took place in Cyprus and collected domestic UCOs from local schools. Funds obtained from
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sales were then reinvested in the participating schools. To date, over 200k euros have been redistributed for environmental education, green infrastructure and technology in said schools. This example shows how waste collection and valorisation practices can bring developments from environmental, economic and social perspectives.⁶³ Despite all these synergies, in terms of sustainability and the SDG targets here evaluated, few trade-offs were identified. These trade-offs are mainly related to the final product (PP) properties regardless of its origin - while recyclable, this plastic is non-biodegradable and can cause littering in the environment if not properly handled. Furthermore, additives such as phthalates can be toxic and leach into the environment.⁶²

- The value chain with the lowest score is the number 2, which refers to the production of drop-in ethylene-based plastics, such as polyethylene (PE) and ethylene vinyl acetate (EVA) from biobased ethylene, as well as of other plastics from sugar crops (e.g. polylactic acid – PLA). These novel value chains have been gaining much attention due to the benefits of replacing petro-based monomers by biobased ones, such as ethanol and lactic acid obtained by the fermentation of sugars. While synergies exist in terms of boosting rural development, advancing new efficient technologies and avoiding the pollution and environmental impacts of petro-based value chains (e.g. it is reported that 2.5 tons of CO₂ are sequestered for every ton of biobased PE produced⁶⁴), there are various trade-offs to consider as well. For instance, similar as for UCO-PP, biobased PE and EVA have the same issues as petro-based ones, such as the non-biodegradability, persistence in the environment and pollution potential if not properly collected and managed. As PLA is biodegradable, it represents a better option that has been intensely explored and has a growing market, with a CAGR estimated in 10-15%. The packaging industry is one of the largest consumers of PLA, accounting for ca. 68% of the PLA market in 2021 in terms of revenue.⁶⁵ Another promising technology is PEF (polyethylene furanoate), a 100% plant-based polyester with great potential to replace PET in food packaging applications such as bottles and coatings. Besides the biobased origin, PEF has better mechanical, barrier, and thermal properties than PET, being also recyclable. An externally conducted LCA shows significant reductions in greenhouse gases emissions (-33%), as well as a 45% lower consumption of finite resources, when benchmarking PEF against fossil-based PET. On the contrary, PEF-based bottles performed worse in impact categories linked to agricultural activities (i.e. acidification, terrestrial eutrophication, and land and water use). However, these impact categories were reported to have a minor relevance within the total environmental footprint.⁴⁷ A big issue encompassing all said materials is the feedstock used, which at the current stage primary dedicated sugar crops. There are strong social issues related to the sugar value chain around the world (human trafficking and exploitation, child labour, lack of labour rights and regulations), as well as environmental impacts due to the intensive monoculture causing soil depletion and contamination with pesticides. Finally, these value chains are directly competing with food and feed, a discouraged feedstock in comparison with residual biomasses and organic wastes. Main stakeholders claim that, when fully technologically developed, materials such as green PE and PEF will be also produced from cellulose, which is abundant in non-edible biomass such as agricultural and forestry waste streams. Such advance will bring new synergies and certainly increase the sustainability aspect of the materials.
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Textiles sector

Figure 14. Normalised score per value chain in the textiles sector.

- Overall, this sector had the lowest scores, except for the value chains 2 and 3, which is related to more sustainable feedstocks in the EU context, and new spinning/recycling technologies for textile wastes. Examples are technologies able that obtain cellulosic fibres by mechanically treating pulp and cellulosic wastes (without the use of harmful chemicals), and recycling processes for the recovery of regenerated fibres (e.g. viscose, lyocell, modal, acetate) and re-introduction of such fibres in the textile value chain.^{66,67} Given the extremely high impact of the textile industry (further detailed below), technologies able to close the loop by recycling, using lignocellulosic wastes as feedstock (rather than virgin wood and cotton, for instance), save water and energy, and avoid the usage of toxic chemicals, are very synergic with the environmental and economic sustainability dimensions addressed by the SDG targets. Furthermore, as the textile market is very large and valuable, such advances receive large support from brands and are expanding rapidly. This translates into job creation, more infrastructure for research, training and the development of high-end technologies to replace the traditional and heavily polluting textile processes. For these reasons, no substantial trade-offs were identified for such circular value chains.
- The value chain 3 refers to textiles produced from other natural fibres than cotton, particularly flax (linen). In the EU context, this shift of feedstock is very positive, as it decreases the dependency in complicated supply chains such as cotton, which is largely imported, water and energy intensive, typically uses toxic chemicals and is related to several social issues in growing regions around the world. Linen is a versatile, strong natural fibre made from the cellulose fibres that grows inside of the flax plant's stalks. Europe is a core region for flax cultivation, thanks to its temperate oceanic climate and a rich soil; in fact, 80% of the world's production takes place in European countries – mostly France, Belgium and Netherlands – on around 100,000 hectares, where 3.7 tonnes of CO₂ can be sequestered per hectare.⁶⁸ As such, linen can be produced locally, generate jobs, demands less water than cotton, is recyclable, and can be grown without pesticides. A key reason why linen is such a sustainable fabric is because the entire flax plant can be woven into a fibre, which means that almost no waste is left over from the spinning and weaving process. If organically processed without chemicals or intensive dyes, it also means no water pollution is made.⁶⁹ Finally, the necessary energy to produce linen is substantially lower

when compared to cotton (five times lower); man-made viscose (ten times lower); and synthetic fibres such as polyester (twelve times lower) and nylon (twenty-five times lower).⁷⁰ Therefore, there is a strong case for the development of textile value chains in EU using linen and for a stronger regulation and certification schemes for imported natural fibres, as for now, the low cost competitiveness hinders the growth of this local and more sustainable alternative.

- The value chains 1 and 4 are related to traditional industries (cotton and wood-based fibres, respectively). These biobased products are advantageous in many aspects when compared with synthetic fibres (e.g. polyesters and nylon), for example, five times more energy is needed to produce nylon when compared with cotton.⁷⁰ Furthermore, natural fibres can sequester carbon during the growth of the feedstock. Despite these positive points, the trade-offs of traditional textile industries are major, with a high energy and water usage, release of microfibers release into the ocean (0.5 million tonnes estimated per year), 10% share of global greenhouse gas emissions and the intensive use of toxic, persistent chemicals that can bioaccumulate in the human organism and also cause major pollution of freshwater supplies around the world. As textiles are largely produced in impoverished regions where regulations and control are often lacking, contaminated wastewater is discharged (largely untreated) into groundwater with a high pH and temperature, as well as chemical load.^{70,71} The regulatory issues go beyond the environment, and human exploitation within the textile industry is a largely reported problem. Unfortunately, companies are often not socially responsible, and will exhaust garment factory workers to profit more at a fast pace. By outsourcing supply chain factories, numerous labour rights violations in developing countries occur. Most workforce in the garment industry are women, and child labour is common practice. The profound discrimination that these groups face makes them particularly vulnerable to abuse and exploitation in the garment industry.^{20,21} In terms of feedstock, there are several social issues also related to the cotton supply chain (child labour, human exploitation, lack of labour rights and so on⁷²), further lowering its score. In the case of wood-based (also called man-made or regenerated fibres), social issues are not as relevant due to the better regulated forestry value chains in EU. Nonetheless, trade-offs exist due to the toxic chemicals needed to produce regenerated fibres and their energy-intensive processes. For example, the viscose process requires large amounts of caustic soda (0.5-0.8kg per kg of fibre), as well as carbon disulphide and sulfuric acid, which are toxic and corrosive chemicals.⁷³ These issues and the fact that EU is a large importer of textiles makes this sector problematic in many aspects. There is a current pressure to implement tighter regulations, certification schemes and promote circularity in this sector, and efforts go in the direction of avoiding fast-fashion and mass consumerism to promote local and certified labels, natural fibres organically, ethically and locally produced, and the reuse and recycling of clothing rather than disposal.
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Woodworking sector

Figure 15. Normalised score per value chain in the woodworking sector.

- The value chains evaluated in the woodworking sector had overall similar good scores, showing that, for the most part, they are positively correlated with the applicable SDG targets. When comparing them, it does make sense, as they all refer to the use of side streams (i.e., lignocellulosic residues such as wheat straw; wood residues from timber; and sawdust) for fibreboards, particleboards, and various woodworking products used for interiorism, decoration, crates and cases, etc. Besides the positive circularity aspect of integrating side streams, otherwise discarded or burned, into valuable products, such products can potentially replace petro-based materials of high environmental impact, such as concrete, durable plastics, and metals. The only ambiguity identified is related to the resins used in wood-based panels (particleboards, fibreboards), which are non-biodegradable and still heavily based in formaldehyde, which can be released over time and pollute the environment. Finally, a possible trade-off of the wood-based value chains 2 and 3 is deforestation, which happens in regions where control is difficult and/or inefficient.⁷⁴ If the timber industry remains self-sufficient in Europe²², it is expected a great synergy in all wood-based value chains, as a locally source feedstock is overall more sustainable, will boost regional economic and social development by creating jobs and infrastructure, and will allow for an easier control under EU regulations, avoiding pressing issues such as deforestation and loss of biodiversity, as well as human rights violations. This is also the case for value chain 1, based in lignocellulosic residues (particularly wheat straw), where EU is considered self-sufficient too.⁷⁵

Pulp & paper sector

Figure 16. Normalised score per value chain in the pulp & paper sector.

- The value chains evaluated in this sector had overall great scores. Except for number 4, the scores were >85%. Accordingly, the three value chains with high scores are related to resistant packaging made from mechanical wood pulp or semi-chemical wood pulp (1), recycled paper for graphic purposes (2), and specialty cellulose / novel microfibrillated and nanocrystalline cellulosic materials (3). As with other materials, recycling of paper is a beneficial activity thinking on the circularity aspect, being as well more established and easier considering cardboard and other “pure” paper grades not containing synthetic coatings). Importantly, in the hierarchy of the circular economy, a change from material recycling to product reuse is favoured, as recycling has impacts due to the water and energy needed. Nonetheless, when compared to the production of new paper, recycling is positive and synergic with most of the selected SDG targets.⁷⁶ The waste valorisation aspect might bring developments, income and jobs to small actors decentralized in the value chain (e.g. collectors and municipalities). The identified trade-off of this value chain is extended to all value chains of the pulp & paper sector, and is related to the high water usage of such processes. Every year, the pulp and paper industry consumes billions of cubic metres of water, producing huge amounts of polluted wastewater. This sector is considered the world’s third biggest industrial wastewater producer.⁷⁷ Conventional wastewater treatments require a high energy input and have a debatable environmental impact. Alternative technologies for wastewater treatment are arising, such as novel oxidation / flocculation routes and even microbial fuel cells (MFCs) able to produce energy, but limitations still need to be overcome for a scale-up to industrial level (mainly the isolation of bacterial consortia able to adapt to the severe conditions, degrade toxic compounds present in effluents, and express electrogenic activity).⁷⁷
- Traditional mechanical / semi-chemical pulping (value chain 1) to produce resistant packaging are relatively mild processes, as the harsh bleaching and delignification chemicals are not necessary. Furthermore, there is a high incentive for shifting from traditional plastic packaging (non-biodegradable, petro-based, and obtained via resource-intensive processes) to paper-based packaging solutions, an overall more sustainable alternative. In the case of high-purity cellulosic materials (specialty cellulose, MFCs, CNCs, represented by value chain

3), chemical-intensive and energy-intensive steps are required to isolate the cellulose fraction from the initial (woody) biomass. Despite such process-related trade-offs, there are several synergies when taking into consideration the wide range of application of such cellulosic materials, which goes from coatings for food packaging (to achieve the required barrier properties and effectively replace plastics), valuable ingredients for the food, pharma, and cosmetic industries (thickeners, rheology modifiers, surfactants and so on), building blocks for biocompatible composites to replace metals and plastics, building blocks for sustainable electronics, etc.^{78–82} Accordingly, cellulosic materials have the benefits of being 100% biobased, safe, and have tuneable properties that are in the spotlight to replace several highly polluting and bioaccumulative petro-based chemicals and materials. Furthermore, novel biorefining concepts target the full valorisation of biomass, extending the product portfolio to other interesting fractions such as lignin and hemicelluloses, which also have exploitable properties to serve as a resource of fine chemicals, energy dense fuels, and materials.⁸³ Such emerging, high-tech fields boost research, create jobs and novel infrastructures aiming the development of more sustainable value chains. Despite being energy intensive, efforts in the pulp and paper industries (PPI) in the Northern EU, a well-established sector, show a growing compromise with the energy transition. For example, a report focused in the Swedish and Finnish landscape reported major improvements energy efficiency, switching to bio-based fuels, and increasing on-site renewable electricity production. Electricity and primary energy consumption in the PPI decreased substantially in both countries.⁸⁴ Responsible pulp and paper operations can bring many benefits to forests, local economies, and people, particularly in rural areas. Many pulp and paper companies are demonstrating leadership in responsible forestry and plantation management, as well as in clean manufacturing processes and recycled content.

- The value chain 4 refers to the use of lignocellulosic residue as a source of cellulosic fibres, which is a great alternative to virgin wood and brings various synergies with the selected SDGs (circularity, industry diversification, rural development, and new source of income to producers). In this context, a target feedstock is sugarcane bagasse, an abundant and underutilised agricultural residue from the sugar value chain that contains relevant amounts of cellulose (ca. 40wt%).⁸⁵ The trade-offs that lowered the score of this value chain are mainly social, as the sugarcane industry is linked to several violation of human rights, such as women exploitation, deforestation, forced displacement of communities, slavery and child labour. In the EU context, such value chains would be largely dependent on feedstock importing, thus requiring the reinforcement of strict regulations to ensure the protection of workers and local development, constant audits of the supply chain, and proper stakeholder's accountability to prevent malpractices in least-developed countries.

Sector overview

Figure 17 shows an overview of the normalised scores per sector. As discussed throughout this section, highly synergic biobased value chains were observed in the construction, woodworking, and pulp and paper sectors, which have the overall benefits of a more established and regulated supply chain in EU, less usage of toxic chemicals, and technologies that ensure circularity and sustainability by the reintegration of waste streams into products. The low-to-medium scores (57-70%) of value chains within the textiles, chemicals and plastics sectors are mainly related to the following trade-offs *i)* known social and environmental issues in some supply chains, particularly in the case of sugar/cotton industries and textiles manufacturing, where EU largely depends on importing and competition with food occurs; *ii)* the use of polluting chemicals in biobased value chains, and the energy- and water-intensive character of some processes; *iii)* the non-biodegradability and difficult

recyclability of some biobased products; *iv*) the challenges on manufacturing 100% biobased products that meet product specifications, leading to partial replacement in most cases. Nonetheless, the advances within all sectors are promising, with several technological and business developments moving towards circular processes and the production of carbon neutral/negative products to replace fossil-based value chains, promote local developments, empower communities, and improve the processes efficiency and sustainability profiles. Furthermore, the implementation of novel regulatory frameworks, regional bioeconomy clusters and certification schemes are paramount to promote the timely development of novel sustainable, holistic value chains that not only bring environmental benefits, but also guarantee economic and social developments throughout the whole supply chain by taking into consideration regional particularities and potential.

Figure 17. Normalised score per industrial sector.

4. Conclusions

In this work, a range of sustainability targets from the seventeen Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) defined by the United Nations were selected with a focus on four main sustainability dimensions, namely: Environmental, Circularity, Social, and Economic. The analysis of the SDG targets against the sustainability dimensions compiled for biobased products (in D1.2) allowed the identification of the most relevant SDG targets. As a result of the matching, all the SDGs were found relevant. The 17 SDGs comprise a total of 169 targets, of which from the matching 85 were identified to be most relevant for analysing sustainability of biobased products. It is seen that SDGs 2 and 7 have all their targets matched to criteria, while SDGs 6, 8, and 9 present a 75% of targets matched. On the other hand, SDGs 4 and 17 have the lowest coverage with 14% and 16%, respectively.

These selected SDG targets were then correlated with 25 biobased value chains selected as representative examples within the six industrial sectors of highest relevance in the EU context for biobased industry, namely chemicals, construction, plastics, textiles, woodworking, and pulp & paper. Each one of the representative value chains was evaluated qualitatively with respect to each SDG target to identify synergies and trade-offs between them. From the 85 matching SDG targets, 43 were found applicable to the representative biobased value chains.

The results show that high synergies are seen for the SDG targets with the assessed biobased value chains, particularly the ones using waste as feedstock (instead of primary resources such as starch crops, sugar crops, and virgin wood). Technological advances and a more holistic view are enabling the replacement of resource-intensive materials and chemicals, traditionally derived from petroleum, by solutions obtained from biological resources that might have other positive properties such as recyclability, biodegradability, and non-toxicity. Said developments are well aligned with the EU bioeconomy strategy when considering wastes and residues as resources and obtaining biobased products with a high value and competitive performance. Nonetheless, it is important to point out that not many value chains address the end of life of its products, which can cause pollution and bioaccumulation (even if 100% biobased). It is, therefore, essential to consider the full sustainability of a product since its design, including an end-of-life assessment with reuse, recycling, and responsible disposal strategies.

The sustainability of some sectors will largely benefit from locally sourced feedstocks (e.g. textiles from flax instead of cotton in EU), which can boost local economies, create jobs, and allow for an easier control and regulation. This demands major changes in terms of policy, as current challenges for implementing circular strategies are related to unfavourable policies that make locally sourced products often less cost competitive. Nonetheless, as the transition to a bioeconomy is a global mission where regions with strong agricultural and forestry commodity sectors will play a big role, strict regulations and strategies must be put into place to prevent human rights violations and environmental drawbacks well-known in said sectors, which are major trade-offs. In this context, having strong sustainability certification schemes applied to these sectors will help ensuring a transition to more sustainable operations.

Besides considering social aspects, product eco-design, policymaking, and developing cascading processes and efficient technologies, the establishment of regional clusters and certification schemes are very important for establishing a circular bioeconomy. These instruments will facilitate the transition by i) adapting the bioeconomy concept to each local context, taking into consideration regional particularities, weaknesses and strengths; ii) intensifying the cooperation with the waste management sector to ensure that biobased products can be integrated in collection, separation, recycling and composting schemes; and iii) standardizing all sustainability-related information,

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making regulation and control easier and facilitating the implementation and acceptance of novel value chains by all stakeholders (governments, industrial actors) and by society.

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Annex

Table 5. Matching between SDG targets and sustainability principles and criteria of biobased systems.

SDG	TARGETS	Environmental Sustainability Principle												Circularity Principle									
		Reduce GHG emissions	Conserve land with high carbon stock and peatland	Promote sustainable forest management	Promote the positive and reduce the negative impacts on ecosystems and biodiversity	Conserve and protect water resources	Protect soil quality and productivity	Implement best practices for the use of (agro)chemicals	Restrict air pollution, promote good air quality	Limit the risk of Indirect Land Use Change	Promote responsible waste management	Promote efficient use of energy and material resources			Promote material circularity								
		Lifecycle GHG emissions	Protection of land with high carbon stock	Protection of peatland	Maintaining forest productivity	Protection of land with a high biodiversity value	Restoration, preservation and strengthening of biodiversity	Sustainable use of water	Maintaining and enhancing water quality	Maintaining and enhancing soil quality	Use of residual flows	Prohibition on the use of hazardous/toxic chemicals	Use, storage, handling and disposal of agrochemicals	Air quality	Restriction on open-air burning	ILUC Low Risk	Waste management	Valorization of residual flows	Raw material efficiency	Efficient use of energy	Use of renewable and non-renewable sources	Material circularity	
1 NO POVERTY	1.1 Eradicate extreme poverty.																						
	1.2 Reduce poverty by at least 50%.																						
	1.3 Implement social protection systems.																						
	1.4 Equal rights to ownership, basic services, technology, and economic resources.																						
	1.5 Build resilience to environmental, economic, and social disasters.																						
2 ZERO HUNGER	1.4 Mobilize resources to implement policies to end poverty.																						
	1.8 Create pro-poor and gender-sensitive policy frameworks.																						
	2.1 Universal access to safe and nutritious food.																						
	2.2 End all forms of malnutrition.																						
	2.3 Double the productivity and incomes of small-scale food producers.																						
3 GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING	2.4 Sustainable food production and resilient agricultural practices.																						
	2.5 Maintain the genetic diversity in food production.																						
	2.A Invest in rural infrastructure, agricultural research, technology, and gene banks.																						
	2.B Prevent agricultural trade restrictions, market distortions and export subsidies.																						
	2.C Ensure stable food commodity markets and timely access to information.																						
	3.1 Reduce maternal mortality.																						
	3.2 End all preventable deaths under 5 years of age.																						
	3.3 Fight communicable diseases.																						
	3.4 Reduce mortality from non-communicable diseases and promote mental health.																						
	3.5 Prevent and treat substance abuse.																						
4 QUALITY EDUCATION	3.6 Reduce road injuries and deaths.																						
	3.7 Universal access to sexual and reproductive care, family planning and education.																						
	3.8 Achieve universal health coverage.																						
	3.9 Reduce illnesses and death from hazardous chemicals and pollution.																						
	3.A Implement the WHO framework convention on tobacco control.																						
	3.B Support research, development and universal access to affordable vaccines and medicines.																						
	3.C Increase health financing and support health workforce in developing countries.																						
	3.D Improve early warning systems for global health risks.																						
	4.1 Free primary and secondary education.																						
	4.2 Equal access to quality pre-primary education.																						
5 GENDER EQUALITY	4.3 Equal access to affordable technical, vocational and higher education.																						
	4.4 Increase the number of people with relevant skills for financial success.																						
	4.5 Eliminate all discrimination in education.																						
	4.6 Universal literacy and numeracy.																						
	4.7 Education for sustainable development and global citizenship.																						
	4.8 Build and upgrade inclusive and safe schools.																						
	4.9 Expand higher education scholarships for developing countries.																						
	4.A Increase the supply of qualified teachers in developing countries.																						
	5.1 End discrimination against women and girls.																						
	5.2 End all violence against and exploitation of women and girls.																						
5.3 Eliminate forced marriages and genital mutilation.																							
5.4 Value unpaid care and promote shared domestic responsibilities.																							
5.5 Ensure full participation in leadership and decision-making.																							
5.6 Universal access to reproductive health and rights.																							
5.7 Equal rights to economic resources, property ownership and financial services																							
5.8 Promote empowerment of women through technology																							
5.9 Adopt and strengthen policies and enforceable legislation for gender equality																							

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SDG	TARGETS	Social sustainability principle																	
		Labour rights						Working conditions					Property and usage rights		Wellbeing of the local population			Food security	
		Child labour	Forced and compulsory labour	Fair salary, Remuneration	Association and collective bargaining rights	Equal opportunities /discrimination	Grievance mechanism	Contract	Training	Occupational health and safety	Harassment, violence	Hours of work and overtime	Land use rights (including land tenure)	Water use rights	Health and safety of local community	Local services health, education, infrastructure -3/ Prosperity	Local values	Community involvement	
1 NO POVERTY	1.1 Eradicate extreme poverty.																		
	1.2 Reduce poverty by at least 50%.																		
	1.3 Implement social protection systems.																		
	1.4 Equal rights to ownership, basic services, technology, and economic resources.																		
	1.5 Build resilience to environmental, economic, and social disasters.																		
2 ZERO HUNGER	1.A Mobilize resources to implement policies to end poverty.																		
	1.B Create pro-poor and gender-sensitive policy frameworks.																		
	2.1 Universal access to safe and nutritious food.																		
	2.2 End all forms of malnutrition.																		
	2.3 Double the productivity and incomes of small-scale food producers.																		
3 GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING	2.4 Sustainable food production and resilient agricultural practice.																		
	2.5 Maintain the genetic diversity in food production.																		
	2.A Invest in rural infrastructure, agricultural research, technology, and gene banks.																		
	2.B Prevent agricultural trade restrictions, market distortions and export subsidies.																		
	2.C Ensure stable food commodity markets and timely access to information.																		
	3.1 Reduce maternal mortality.																		
	3.2 End all preventable deaths under 5 years of age.																		
	3.3 Fight communicable diseases.																		
	3.4 Reduce mortality from non-communicable diseases and promote mental health.																		
	3.5 Prevent and treat substance abuse.																		
	3.6 Reduce road injuries and deaths.																		
	3.7 Universal access to sexual and reproductive care, family planning and education.																		
	3.8 Achieve universal health coverage.																		
3.9 Reduce illnesses and death from hazardous chemicals and pollution.																			
3.A Implement the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control.																			
3.B Support research, development and universal access to affordable vaccines and medicines.																			
3.C Increase health financing and support health workforce in developing countries.																			
3.D Improve early warning systems for global health risks.																			
4 QUALITY EDUCATION	4.1 Free primary and secondary education.																		
	4.2 Equal access to quality pre-primary education.																		
	4.3 Equal access to affordable technical, vocational and higher education.																		
	4.4 Increase the number of people with relevant skills for financial success.																		
	4.5 Eliminate all discrimination in education.																		
	4.6 Universal literacy and numeracy.																		
	4.7 Education for sustainable development and global citizenship.																		
	4.8 Build and upgrade inclusive and safe schools.																		
4.9 Expand higher education scholarships for developing countries.																			
4.A Increase the supply of qualified teachers in developing countries.																			
5 GENDER EQUALITY	5.1 End discrimination against women and girls.																		
	5.2 End all violence against and exploitation of women and girls.																		
	5.3 Eliminate forced marriages and genital mutilation.																		
	5.4 Value unpaid care and promote shared domestic responsibilities.																		
	5.5 Ensure full participation in leadership and decision-making.																		
	5.6 Universal access to reproductive health and rights.																		
	5.7 Equal rights to economic resources, property ownership and financial services.																		
	5.8 Promote empowerment of women through technology.																		
	5.9 Adopt and strengthen policies and enforceable legislation for gender equality.																		

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SDG	TARGETS	Economic sustainability principle							
		Financial and economic viability	Fair business practices, Integrity /fraudulent	Inclusive economic growth		Use of knowledge and technology		Fair trade and market practices	Risk assessment and management
				Local employment and procurement	Community investment	Compensate indigenous knowledge	Use of technology		
1 NO POVERTY	1.1 Eradicate extreme poverty.								
	1.2 Reduce poverty by at least 50%.								
	1.3 Implement social protection systems.								
	1.4 Equal rights to ownership, basic services, technology, and economic resources.								
	1.5 Build resilience to environmental, economic, and social disasters.								
	1.A Mobilize resources to implement policies to end poverty.								
	1.B Create pro-poor and gender-sensitive policy frameworks.								
	2.1 Universal access to safe and nutritious food.								
	2.2 End all forms of malnutrition.								
	2.3 Double the productivity and incomes of small-scale food producers.								
2.4 Sustainable food production and resilient agricultural practices.									
2.5 Maintain the genetic diversity in food production.									
2.A Invest in rural infrastructure, agricultural research, technology, and gene banks.									
2.B Prevent agricultural trade restrictions, market distortions and export subsidies.									
2.C Ensure stable food commodity markets and timely access to information.									
3.1 Reduce maternal mortality.									
3.2 End all preventable deaths under 5 years of age.									
3.3 Fight communicable diseases.									
3.4 Reduce mortality from non-communicable diseases and promote mental health.									
3.5 Prevent and treat substance abuse.									
3.6 Reduce road injuries and deaths.									
3.7 Universal access to sexual and reproductive care, family planning and education.									
3.8 Achieve universal health coverage.									
3.9 Reduce illnesses and death from hazardous chemicals and pollution.									
3.A Implement the who framework convention in tobacco control.									
3.B Support research, development and universal access to affordable vaccines and medicines.									
3.C Increase health financing and support health workforce in developing countries.									
3.D Improve early warning systems for global health risks.									
4.1 Free primary and secondary education.									
4.2 Equal access to quality pre-primary education.									
4.3 Equal access to affordable technical, vocational and higher education.									
4.4 Increase the number of people with relevant skills for financial success.									
4.5 Eliminate all discrimination in education.									
4.6 Universal literacy and numeracy.									
4.7 Education for sustainable development and global citizenship.									
4.8 Build and upgrade inclusive and safe schools.									
4.9 Expand higher education scholarships for developing countries.									
4.A Increase the supply of qualified teachers in developing countries.									
5.1 End discrimination against women and girls.									
5.2 End all violence against and exploitation of women and girls.									
5.3 Eliminate forced marriages and genital mutilation.									
5.4 Value unpaid care and promote shared domestic responsibilities.									
5.5 Ensure full participation in leadership and decision-making.									
5.6 Universal access to reproductive health and rights.									
5.7 Equal rights to economic resources, property ownership and financial services									
5.8 Promote empowerment of women through technology									
5.9 Adopt and strengthen policies and enforceable legislation for gender equality									

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<p>6 CLEAN WATER AND SANITATION</p> <p>6.1 Safe and affordable drinking water. 6.2 End open defecation and provide access to sanitation and hygiene. 6.3 Improve water quality, wastewater treatment and safe reuse. 6.4 Increase water-use efficiency and ensure freshwater supplies. 6.5 Implement integrated water resources management. 6.6 Protect and restore water-related ecosystems. 6.7 Expand water and sanitation support to developing countries. 6.8 Support local engagement in water and sanitation management.</p>																						
<p>7 AFFORDABLE AND CLEAN ENERGY</p> <p>7.1 Universal access to modern energy. 7.2 Increase global percentage of renewable energy. 7.3 Double the improvement in energy efficiency. 7.4 Promote access to research, technology and investments in clean energy. 7.5 Expand and upgrade energy services for developing countries.</p>																						
<p>8 DECENT WORK AND ECONOMIC GROWTH</p> <p>8.1 Sustainable economic growth. 8.2 Diversify, innovate and upgrade for economic productivity. 8.3 Promote policies to support job creation and growing enterprises. 8.4 Improve resource efficiency in consumption and production. 8.5 Full employment and decent work with equal pay. 8.6 Promote youth employment, education and training. 8.7 End modern slavery, trafficking and child labour. 8.8 Protect labour rights and promote safe working environments. 8.9 Promote beneficial and sustainable tourism. 8.A Universal access to banking, insurance and financial services. 8.B Increase aid for trade support. 8.C Develop a global youth employment strategy.</p>																						
<p>9 INDUSTRY AND INFRASTRUCTURE</p> <p>9.1 Develop sustainable, resilient, and inclusive infrastructures. 9.2 Promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization. 9.3 Increase Access to financial services and markets. 9.4 Upgrade all industries and infrastructures for sustainability. 9.5 Enhance research and upgrade industrial technologies. 9.6 Facilitate sustainable infrastructure development for developing countries 9.7 Support domestic technology development and industrial diversification 9.8 Universal Access to information and communications technology.</p>																						
<p>10 REDUCED INEQUALITIES</p> <p>10.1 Reduce income inequalities 10.2 Promote universal social, economic and political inclusion. 10.3 Ensure equal opportunities and end discrimination. 10.4 Adopt fiscal and social policies that promote equality. 10.5 Improved regulation of global financial markets and institutions. 10.6 Enhanced representation for developing countries in financial institutions. 10.7 Responsible and well-managed migration policies. 10.8 Special and differential treatment for developing countries. 10.9 Encourage development assistance and investment in least developed countries. 10.A Reduce transaction costs for migrant remittances.</p>																						
<p>11 SUSTAINABLE CITIES AND COMMUNITIES</p> <p>11.1 Safe and affordable housing. 11.2 Affordable and sustainable transport systems. 11.3 Inclusive and sustainable urbanization. 11.4 Protect the world's cultural and natural heritage. 11.5 Reduce the adverse effects of natural disasters. 11.6 Reduce the environmental impact of cities. 11.7 Provide Access to safe and inclusive green and public spaces. 11.A Strong national and regional development planning. 11.B Implement policies for inclusion resource efficiency and disaster risk reduction. 11.C Support least developed countries in sustainable and resilient building.</p>																						

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SDG	Target	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	
12 RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION	12.1 Implement the 10 year sustainable consumption and production framework																		
	12.2 Sustainable management and use of natural resources																		
	12.3 Halve global per capita food waste																		
	12.4 Responsible management of chemicals and waste																		
	12.5 Substantially reduce waste generation																		
	12.6 Encourage companies to adopt sustainable practices and sustainability reporting																		
	12.7 Promote sustainable public procurement practices																		
	12.8 Promote universal understanding of sustainable lifestyles																		
	12.A Support developing countries' scientific and technological capacity for sustainable consumption and production																		
	12.B Develop and implement tools to monitor sustainable tourism																		
	12.C Remove market distortion that encourage wasteful consumption																		
	13 CLIMATE ACTION	13.1 Strengthen resilience and adaptive capacity to climate related disasters																	
13.2 Integrate climate change measures into policies and planning																			
13.3 Build knowledge and capacity to climate change																			
13.A Implement the UN Framework convention on climate change																			
13.B Promote mechanisms to raise capacity for planning and management																			
14 LIFE BELOW WATER	14.1 Reduce marine pollution																		
	14.2 Protect and restore ecosystems																		
	14.3 Reduce ocean acidification																		
	14.4 Sustainable fishing																		
	14.5 Conserve coastal and marine areas																		
	14.6 End subsidies contributing to overfishing																		
	14.7 Increase the economic benefits from sustainable use of marine resources																		
	14.A Increase scientific knowledge, research and technology for ocean health																		
	14.B Support small scale fishers																		
14.C Implement and enforce international sea law																			
15 LIFE OF LAND	15.1 Conserve and restore terrestrial and freshwater ecosystem																		
	15.2 End deforestation and restore degraded forests																		
	15.3 End desertification and restore degraded land																		
	15.4 Ensure conservation of mountain ecosystem																		
	15.5 Protect biodiversity and natural habitats																		
	15.6 Promote Access to genetic resources and fair sharing of the benefits																		
	15.7 Eliminate poaching and trafficking of protected species																		
	15.8 Prevent invasive alien species on land																		
	15.9 Integrate ecosystems in government planning																		
	15.A Increase financial resources to conserve and sustainably use ecosystem and biodiversity																		
16 PEACE, JUSTICE, AND INSTITUTIONS	16.1 Reduce violence everywhere																		
	16.2 Protect children from abuse, exploitation, trafficking and violence																		
	16.3 Promote the rule of law and ensure equal access to justice																		
	16.4 Combat organized crime and illicit financial and arms flows																		
	16.5 Substantially reduce corruption and bribery																		
	16.6 Develop effective, accountable, and transparent institutions																		
	16.7 Ensure responsive, inclusive, and representative decision-making																		
	16.8 Strengthen the participation in global governance																		
	16.9 Provide universal legal identity																		
	16.A Ensure public access to information and protect fundamental freedoms																		
17 PARTNERSHIP FOR THE GOALS	17.1 Mobilize resources to improve domestic revenue collection																		
	17.2 Implement all development assistance commitments																		
	17.3 Mobilize financial resources for developing countries																		
	17.4 Assist developing countries in attaining debt sustainability																		
	17.5 Invest in least developed countries																		
	17.6 Knowledge sharing and cooperation for access to science, technology and innovation																		
	17.7 Promote sustainable technologies to developing countries																		
	17.8 Strengthen the science, technology and innovation capacity for least developed countries																		
	17.9 Enhance SDG capacity in developing countries																		
	17.A Promote a universal trading system under the WTO																		
	17.B Increase the exports of developing countries																		
	17.C Remove trade barriers for least developed countries																		

Table 6. Qualitative analyses of selected value chains against the applicable SDG targets.

		SDG target		
		1.4	2.3	2.4
SECTOR	Value chains			
CHEMICALS	1 Novel and drop-in chemical building blocks (e.g. ethylene, succinic acid, ethylene glycol, lactic acid) from sugars	na	na	-
	2 Novel and drop-in chemical building blocks (e.g. dicarboxylic acids, glycols, diols) from residual biomass	+	+	+/-
	3 Novel resins from forest residues	na	na	na
	4 Oleochemicals (e.g. fatty acids, fatty acids esters, fatty alcohols and glycerine) from residue and waste oils and fats	+	+	na
	5 Oleochemicals from oil crops	na	na	-
	6 Fine chemicals from biobased sources (e.g., vanillin, geraniol, cinnamic acid, geranyl acetate, linalool)	na	+	na
CONSTRUCTION	1 Rigid polyurethane foams (rPUs) using lignin	na	na	na
	2 Fibreboard and concrete using hemp	na	na	na
	3 Oriented strand board from straw	+	+	na
	4 Wood-based particleboards for interior construction	na	na	na
PLASTICS	1 Polypropylene (PP) from used cooking oil	+	na	na
	2 Polyethylene (PE) and ethylene vinyl acetate (EVA) using green ethylene, Polylactic acid (PLA)	na	+	-
	3 Novel composites and thermoplastic materials from waste	+	na	na
	4 Novel bioplastics from biological metabolism (such as PHA)	na	na	na
TEXTILE	1 Cotton textile value chain	na	na	na
	2 Recycling cotton and other cellulose-rich textiles, novel efficient spinning technologies	+	na	na
	3 Textiles from other natural fibers	na	na	na
	4 Traditional cellulosic fibres from wood	na	na	na
WOODWORKING	1 Use of lignocellulosic residues for interiorism and decoration (fibreboards made from hemp, wheat straw)	+	na	na
	2 Particle boards made out of wood for interior construction, carpentry pieces made out of wood (cases, boxes, crates, drums and similar packings)	na	na	na
	3 Use of sawdust and other subproducts in woodworking industry	na	na	na
PULP & PAPER	1 Resistant packaging (cartons, boxes and cases of corrugated paper) from mechanical wood pulp or semi-chemical wood pulp	na	na	na
	2 Recycled paper for graphic purposes	+	na	na
	3 Specialty cellulose, cellulose ethers and cellulose acetate, cellulosic microfibrils (MFCs), and micro-nano cristaline cellulose (MCCs, CNSs)	na	na	na
	4 Napkins and tissues from sugarcane bagasse and other residues	+	+	na

		2.A	2.B	2.C	3.9	4.4	5.2	6.3	6.4	6.8	7.2	7.3	7.4	8.1	8.2	8.3	8.4	8.5	8.6	
SECTOR	V																			
CHEMICALS	1	+	-	-	+/-	+	-	+	-	na	na	na	+	+	+	+	+	+/-	+	
	2	+	na	na	+/-	+	-	+	na	na	na	na	+	+	+	+	+	+/-	+	
	3	+	na	na	+/-	+	na	+	na	na	na	na	na	+	+	+	+	+	+	
	4	na	na	na	+	+	na	+	na	na	na	na	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	
	5	+	-	-	+	+	-	+	-	na	na	na	na	+	na	+	na	+/-	+	
	6	+	na	na	+	+	na	+	-	na	na	na	na	+	+	+	+	+	+	
CONSTRUCTION	1	+	na	na	+/-	+	na	+/-	na	na	na	na	na	+	+	+	+	+	+	
	2	+	na	na	+/-	+	na	na	na	na	na	+	na	+	+	na	+	+	+	
	3	+	na	na	+/-	na	+	+	na	+	+/-	+								
	4	+	na	na	+/-	na	+	na	na	na	+	+								
PLASTICS	1	na	na	na	+/-	+	na	+/-	na	na	na	na	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	
	2	+	-	-	+/-	+	-	+/-	-	na	na	na	+	+	+	+	+	+/-	+	
	3	na	na	na	+	+	na	+/-	na	na	na	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	
	4	na	na	na	+	+	na	+	na	+	na	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	
TEXTILE	1	+	na	na	+/-	na	-	+	-	na	na	+	na	+	na	na	na	-	+	
	2	na	na	na	+	+	na	+	+	na	na	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	
	3	+	na	na	+	na	na	+	+	na	na	+	na	+	+	+	+	+	+	
	4	+	na	na	+/-	na	-	+/-	-	na	na	+/-	+	+	+	na	na	+/-	+	
WOODWORKING	1	+	na	na	+/-	na	+	+	na	+	+	+								
	2	+	na	na	+/-	na	na	+	na	na	na	na	na	+	na	na	na	+	+	
	3	+	na	na	+/-	na	+	+	na	+	+	+								
PULP & PAPER	1	+	na	na	+	na	na	na	-	na	+	+	+	+	+	na	+	+	+	
	2	na	na	na	+	na	na	+	-	na	na	+	+	+	+	na	+	+	+	
	3	+	na	na	+/-	+	na	+	-	na	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	
	4	+	na	na	+/-	+	-	na	-	na	+	+	+	+	+	na	+	+/-	+	

		8.7	8.8	9.1	9.3	9.4	9.5	9.7	11.6	12.2	12.3	12.4	12.5	12.6	13.2	14.1	14.3	
SECTOR	V																	
CHEMICALS	1	-	+/-	+	+	+	+	+	na	+	+	+	na	+	+	+/-	-	
	2	-	+/-	+	+	+	+	+	na	+	na	+	+	+	+	+/-	-	
	3	na	+	+	+	+	+	+	na	+	na	+	+	na	na	-	-	
	4	na	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	na	na	+	+	
	5	-	+/-	+	+	+	+	+	na	+	na	+	na	+	na	+	-	
	6	na	+	+	+	+	+	+	na	+	na	+	+	+	na	+/-	-	
CONSTRUCTION	1	na	+	+	+	+	+	+	na	+	na	-	+	+	na	-	na	
	2	na	na	na	+	+	+	+	na	+	na	+	na	+	na	+	na	
	3	na	na	na	na	+	+	+	na	+	na	+	+	na	na	+	na	
	4	na	na	na	na	+	na	na	na	+	na	+	na	na	+	+	na	
PLASTICS	1	na	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	-		
	2	-	+/-	+	+	+	+	+	na	+	+	-	na	+	+	-	-	
	3	na	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	na	-	+	+	na	+	+	
	4	na	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	na	+	+	
TEXTILE	1	-	+/-	na	na	+	na	na	na	+	na	-	na	+	+	+	-	
	2	na	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	na	+	+	+	na	+	+	
	3	+	+	na	+	+	+	+	na	+	na	+	na	na	na	+	-	
	4	-	+/-	+	na	+	na	na	na	+	na	-	na	+	+	+	-	
WOODWORKING	1	na	na	na	+	+	+	+	na	+	na	+	+	na	na	+	-	
	2	na	na	na	na	+	na	na	na	+	na	+	+	na	na	+	na	
	3	na	na	na	+	+	+	+	na	+	na	+	+	na	na	+	na	
PULP & PAPER	1	na	+	+	na	+	+	+	na	+	na	+	na	+	+	+	+	
	2	na	+	na	na	+	+	+	+	+	na	+	+	na	na	+	na	
	3	na	+	+	+	+	+	+	na	+	na	+	na	na	na	+	na	
	4	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	na	+	na	+	+	+	na	+	na	

		15.2	15.A	15.B	16.2	16.5	17.7
SECTOR	V						
CHEMICALS	1	-	+	na	-	-	+
	2	-	+	na	-	na	+
	3	na	+	+	na	na	+
	4	na	+	na	na	na	+
	5	-	+	na	-	-	+
	6	-	+	na	na	na	+
CONSTRUCTION	1	na	+	+	na	na	+
	2	na	+	na	na	na	+
	3	na	na	na	na	na	na
	4	+	na	na	na	na	na
PLASTICS	1	na	na	na	na	na	+
	2	-	+	na	-	-	+
	3	na	na	na	na	na	+
	4	na	na	na	na	na	+
TEXTILE	1	na	+	na	-	-	na
	2	+	na	na	na	na	+
	3	na	+	na	+	na	+
	4	+/-	+	+	-	-	na
WOODWORKING	1	na	na	na	na	na	na
	2	-	na	na	na	na	na
	3	-	na	na	na	na	na
PULP & PAPER	1	+/-	+	+	na	na	na
	2	+	na	na	na	na	na
	3	+/-	+	+	na	na	+
	4	+	+	na	na	-	+

About SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED is an EU funded (Horizon Europe) project aiming at defining and promoting the adoption of effective and robust sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels for industrial biobased systems to support tracing the sustainability (environmental, social, economic) of biobased products along the value chains and trades within the EU and globally for responsible production and consumption. This objective is realised by the development of a monitoring system, mapping of the current situation in global trade flows of biological resources and biobased products, and feasibility assessment from the adoption of certification schemes and labels considering actual economic as well as internalized environmental and social costs and benefits. The results of the project are leveraged to provide recommendations to four key target groups: policy makers, sustainability system community, industrial biobased value chain actors, and regional bioeconomy stakeholders. These ambitions are addressed by a strong, well-balanced and multi-disciplinary consortium comprised of 5 complementary partners. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED thereby supports the development of harmonized system requirements, continuous improvement of sustainability certification schemes and labels and contributes towards establishing a circular, climate-neutral and sustainable biobased industry.

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